

The trustworthiness landscape in machine learning: a conceptual guide with applications in medicine

Kerstin Lenhof ¹

¹Computational Biology Group, Department of Biosystems Science and Engineering (D-BSSE), ETH Zürich, Basel, Switzerland

²Integrative Bioinformatics Group, Department of Medical Bioinformatics, University Medical Center Göttingen, Georg-August-University Göttingen, Lower Saxony, Germany

³CAIMed – Lower Saxony Center for Artificial Intelligence and Causal Methods in Medicine, Göttingen, Germany

⁴Data Driven Drug Design, Center for Bioinformatics, Saarland Informatics Campus, Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany

⁵Department of Medical Ethics and History of Medicine, University Medical Center Göttingen, Georg-August-University Göttingen, Lower Saxony, Germany

⁶Chair for IT Security, Department of Computer Science, University of Bayreuth, Bavaria, Germany

⁷CISPA Helmholtz Center for Information Security, Saarbrücken, Germany

November 12, 2025

Preprint. This version is uploaded to Zenodo.

Abstract

Trust is a fundamental aspect of all human interactions. As artificial intelligence (AI), particularly the machine learning (ML) realm of AI, increasingly impacts society, this inevitably leads to more human-AI interactions. Thus, finding ways to foster trust in AI and ML models becomes more and more essential, especially since these models permeate sensitive domains such as drug design and medical decision-making.

In this paper, we aim to elucidate how technical design features of ML models can contribute to the trustworthiness of, and trust in, ML models. To this end, we comprehensively surveyed existing work to identify and define various facets of trustworthiness in the ML domain, including, amongst others, generalizability, reliability, robustness, privacy, security, interpretability, explainability, transparency, and fairness. By doing so, we uncover ambiguities in definitions as well as interrelations and tensions between these concepts. We summarize key insights to support researchers in recognizing and developing ML models that are trustworthy within their respective research domains. Additionally, we provide illustrative examples that demonstrate how these concepts can enhance the trustworthiness of ML models in the medical domain.

1 Introduction

Today, almost every academic discipline integrates methods based on artificial intelligence (AI), particularly the machine learning (ML) realm of AI, into their workflows [74, 164]. Here, AI broadly refers to systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human cognition, while ML specifically denotes algorithms and software that learn from data. In the biomedical sciences, for example, AI-assisted workflows have led to an explosion of publications [144], and we can expect this broader trend of AI adoption to persist (see Figure 3 for the temporal development). While ML and related fields have undeniably driven considerable scientific progress [164], concerns about the validity of the results and the usefulness of the derived conclusions for prospective real world scenarios remain justified and affect whether AI is perceived as trustworthy or not. To name just two prominently discussed issues in this context, which directly affect academic research:

Data leakage and reproducibility In 2023, Kapoor and Narayanan found that across a variety of scientific fields, data leakage – roughly corresponding to the inappropriate handling of data before, during, or after the model training process – occurred all over ML-based science and led to overoptimistic claims of model performance [74]. As a consequence, the scientific conclusions drawn from the results achieved by the models may not be reproduced when training and evaluating a similar model adequately. Crucially, Gundersen and Kjensmo found that even reproducing the presented results themselves is often not possible due to insufficient documentation [53]. Recently, Suchak et al. [144] reported that the proliferation of AI-assisted workflows in the biomedical sciences has contributed to a surge in low-quality publications.

Bigger-is-better trend and resource shortage in academia The current *bigger-is-better* trend in AI apparently aggravates the documentation and reproducibility problem: as datasets and models grow in size, so does the documentation debt associated with them [157, 12]. Moreover, the financial, computational, and human resources to train, operate, and maintain such large-scale databases and models on high-performance compute servers often tend to exceed the available resources in academia. This imbalance may compromise the rigor with which these models are developed and deployed, especially given the differing priorities between industry and academia [13]. While the use of open-source pre-trained models (e.g., Google’s BERT model [126]) can reduce the engineering overhead, the documentation debt remains a barrier to reproducibility, and, thus, to successful application of those models. Although recent research demonstrates that scaling models can lead to performance improvements in domains such as natural language processing [73], these scaling trends often do not generalize well to many tasks in medicine and the life sciences. Here, data are often scarce, heterogeneous, and noisy, and simply scaling the models does currently not necessarily lead to better performance (cf. e.g., [50], [37], [168], [167], [145]). Therefore, evaluating models on realistic, well-curated datasets and using decision-mimicking evaluation frameworks are crucial for establishing model trustworthiness [11].

It is apparent and largely justified that these and other issues can cause distrust in such systems, and, as a consequence, in the science and applications based on AI. Indeed, with the growing influence of such models on society, the demand for trust in these systems thus led to the emergence of principled AI frameworks on a political level (see Toreini et al. [151] for a thorough overview on these frameworks). These frameworks are meant to provide general guidelines and policies to ensure what we in this paper refer to as *trustworthy* AI [166, 151], i.e., AI systems that are *worth* of trust in a specific context. Prominently, the AI Act of the EU Commission has claimed to define legal guidance to foster *trustworthy AI* in Europe (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689).

While such frameworks provide high-level objectives and definitions broadly applicable to a variety of contexts where AI is or could be used, this intentional vagueness poses a problem to implementation of *trustworthiness* in practice. In addition, the rapidly expanding body of research on design features linked to trust(worthiness) – such as fairness, interpretability, robustness, reliability, explainability, privacy, security, transparency, and generalizability – can be difficult to navigate not only for newcomers to the field but also for experienced researchers.

In this paper, we aim to elucidate how specific technical design features of ML models may contribute to trust and trustworthiness. To this end, we bridge disciplinary perspectives by integrating insights from the social sciences and humanities with current developments in AI. Overall, this paper should

- serve as a conceptual guide to technical design features of ML systems associated with trustworthiness
- uncover ambiguities between different definitions or understandings of concepts related to trustworthiness, thereby showing their relatedness and tensions
- consequently facilitate the recognition, design, development, and deployment of trustworthy ML systems.

In addition, we present illustrative examples of how these concepts can contribute to making ML models in the life sciences and medical domains more trustworthy.

2 Trust and trustworthiness

Trust and trustworthiness are two terms that we use intuitively and frequently throughout our everyday lives – most likely since trust is required in almost every interaction of an individual (or a group of such) with an entity (e.g., another individual or group) in the real world [58]. Because of this exceptional relevance, there exists ample research across different disciplines, e.g., philosophy, psychology and sociology, regarding the question of how trust(worthiness) can be defined, established and maintained [58, 151]. In medicine and healthcare, for instance, trust is a concept with long-standing meaning. The multifaceted relational nature of trust in the professional-patient relationship within the institutional setting of the healthcare system has been stressed [5]. Interpersonal trust relationships are based on empathy, faith and confidentiality, but also taking dependency and asymmetry within the relationship into account. From this perspective, trust is a moral-emotional attitude of the trusting person (trustor) towards the trusted person (trustee): the trustee’s behavior is evaluated in categories such as truthfulness and non-maleficence. This means, a patient’s trust in a physician’s expertise can be considered as a belief that the physician will help and does not harm. Thus, trust involves the knowledge about one’s own vulnerability and the faith in the goodwill of the other party [8]. At the institutional and societal level, trust, both as an attitude and a practice, can be either encouraged or hindered: For example, trust-building procedures such as confirming shared values, obtaining consent, and communicating under professional secrecy are implemented and part of health ethical policies.

In the following, we strive to give an overview on trust(worthiness) and trust(worthiness)-related properties in the ML context and provide examples of how we may foster trustworthiness of and trust in ML systems that may be used in medicine.

Ever since the high-level expert group (HLEG) of the European commission and similar institutions proposed that AI should be trustworthy and trusted, in particular in high-stakes domains like medicine, there is an ongoing debate about whether the concepts of trust and trustworthiness are

applicable to human–AI relationships, and if so, how these terms should be defined and understood within this context [129, 125, 15]. This debate reflects the broader discussion about the possibility of and conditions for trust in technology, distinguishing between human-like and system-like trust constructs [82, 25]. In particular, Ryan [129] presents a definition of interpersonal trust that ties it to three major aspects, a rational (related to the predicted future behaviour of the entity to be trusted), an affective (related to the goodwill of the entity to be trusted) and a normative one (related to norms, values, and moral status of the entity to be trusted). While AI fulfills the rational account of trust, AI does not possess emotive states (affective aspect) or moral agency (normative aspect) and thus, according to Ryan, cannot be trusted but solely *relied on* [129]. Here, *reliance* is, thus, regarded as equivalent to the rational account of trust. Blanco argues that while motives, e.g., affective and normative ones as discussed by Ryan, are underlying trust relationships, they need not be affective or normative in kind [15] and it is sufficient that the putative user interacts with the AI as if it had motives, i.e., if the user perceives the AI as having motives. While such a definition of trust may not fully capture the nature of human-to-human interaction, it provides a useful starting point for exploring trust in the context of human-AI interaction. In the following, we will explain trust(worthiness) based on descriptions given in Kästner et al. [75], Toreini et al. [151], Hancock et al. [58], Schlicker et al. [133] that are compatible with Blanco’s view on trust.

To this end, we draw on the recently proposed model of trust presented by Hancock et al. [58], which is based on the widely accepted trust model by Mayer [100] who developed it as an operationalizable model in business management (cf. Figure 1 for our overview of this model in the ML context). In their work, Hancock et al. [58] regard trust as an integral part of an interaction between the entity that trusts (the trustor, e.g., a human being) and the entity that is trusted (the trustee, e.g., the ML system), cf. Figure 1. More specifically, the trustor is *willing to* take a certain risk of harm, i.e., is willing to make themselves vulnerable, to interact with the trustee in a specified way in a particular environment. As such, trust can be seen as an attitude of the trustor towards a certain trustee given an environment [75]. From this description it follows that the trustor can grant trust to a trustee with or without justification, and, that the trustor can also deny trust despite good justification in favour of the system. Thus, directly engineering for trust in ML is a difficult endeavour [75]. In particular, the degree to which an ML system will receive trust cannot easily be controlled or merely quantified at its design time. However, what can be controlled at design time are the properties and characteristics of the system, particularly those that make it worth of trust, i.e., *trustworthy*. Kästner et al. [75] propose a context- and stakeholder-dependent definition of trustworthiness for AI systems: "A system S is trustworthy to a stakeholder H in a context C if and only if (a) S works properly in C, and (b) H would be justified to believe that (a) if H came to believe that (a)." In this definition, (a) ensures that the system performs its intended task in the given context, while (b) refers to the properties of a system that enable a specific stakeholder to justifiably believe in its correct functioning. Thus, the key idea is that trustworthiness is not an absolute property of the system, but a relative one depending on the context and, most importantly, on the trustor, i.e., a system may be trustworthy for one trustor and, at the same time, not trustworthy for another one. While (a) is more easily controllable at design time, (b) depends on the trustor and what is justified for them. Indeed, (b) can be very difficult to achieve for all individual trustors and will most likely need to be tailored to trustor groups or hypothetical trustor types, e.g., patients or physicians. In this article, we will discuss how concepts such as privacy, security, generalizability, and explainability relate to (a) and (b). For simplicity, we will also call (a) essentiality and (b) justifiability.

While we hope that trustworthiness-enhancing measures (such as those that we will discuss below) lead to increased levels of trust, their success still depends on the trustor. Here, we would like to emphasize that we can also educate the trustor in a way that increases the likelihood of the trustor

Figure 1: **Trustor-trustee relationship in ML context.** This figure illustrates the relationship between the trustor (human) and the trustee (ML system) in the ML context. We emphasize that regulations, which may be defined based on trustworthiness-properties, play a major role in defining the characteristics of the ML system that the trustor can perceive, and, thus, can influence the level of actual trust given.

perceiving the trustee as trustworthy and, therefore, granting trust [125, 133]. Moreover, trustors do not operate in isolation but in a social and cultural space. They influence each other through interactions, further complicating trust(worthiness) assessment [133].

3 Machine learning concepts related to trustworthiness

To gain a preliminary understanding of how the term trustworthiness is currently used in the context of machine learning, we conducted an exploratory review. Specifically, we performed a Google Scholar search using the query “trustworthiness machine learning” (details provided in the appendix) and reviewed the first 30 results. We emphasize that this is not a systematic review, but rather a narrative synthesis to identify key contributions, recurring themes, and concepts in the area. Fourteen out of the 30 articles were not meeting our inclusion criteria, e.g., because they were not peer-reviewed or did not address the trustworthiness of ML systems (cf. appendix). The remaining 16 papers form the basis for the following discussion of related work relevant to our study.

We find that the terms robustness, fairness, interpretability, explainability, privacy, security, transparency, safety, accountability, integrity, confidentiality, generalizability, reliability, performance, accuracy, confidence, translucency, and auditability have been the focus of at least one of the investigated 16 papers. These findings align well with the concepts that Reinhardt has previously identified as being linked to trustworthy AI in AI ethics guidelines [125] (cf. Table 1 for a comparison).

Table 1: Comparison of concepts identified by Reinhardt [125] and those identified and discussed in this work

Concept	Identified and discussed in this work	Identified by Reinhardt [125]
generalizability	✓	(✓), could be understood as <i>success rate</i>
performance	✓	(✓), could be understood as <i>success rate</i>
accuracy	✓	(✓), could be understood as <i>success rate</i>
reliability	✓	✓
confidence	✓	✗
robustness	✓	✓
fairness	✓	✓
interpretability	✓	✓
explainability	✓	✓
understandability	(✓), could be understood as <i>interpretability/explainability</i>	✓
transparency	✓	✓
translucency	✓	✗
integrity	✓	✗
confidentiality	✓	✗
privacy	✓	✓
security	✓	✓
safety	✓	✓
verficability	✗	✓
auditability	✓	✓
traceability	(✓), linked to <i>auditability</i> and <i>accountability</i> as discussed in this work	✓
accountability	✓	✓
liability	(✓), linked to <i>accountability</i> as discussed in this work	✓
human oversight	(✓), linked to <i>interpretability/explainability/transparency, auditability, and accountability</i> as discussed in this work	✓

Figure 2 shows the frequency with which different terms appear across the 16 analyzed articles. When assessing how often specific terms are at least mentioned, robustness emerges as the most

frequently addressed concept, appearing in 12 out of the 16 articles. In contrast, we can observe that some concepts, i.e., auditability, reliability, confidence, performance, translucency, and accuracy, are not well studied in the top GoogleScholar record list. To obtain a more comprehensive understanding of how often these terms are studied within the (bio)medical and life science literature, we queried PubMed for each of the identified terms of the GoogleScholar search as well as trustworthiness itself and identified all papers that contain "machine learning" and the respective term in their abstract or title. The results are shown in the upper row of Figure 3. We observe that the research interest in ML in general trustworthiness-related terms increased over the years (cf. Figure 3b and 3c). Moreover, we can clearly see that concepts like confidence, safety, interpretability, and reliability are relatively well studied while translucency and auditability are only considered by few studies (cf. Figure 3a). Interestingly, the term trustworthiness itself is also rather poorly studied, as it is only recently that it gained the focus of attention, possibly because of the release of the guidelines to *trustworthy* AI by the HLEG of the European Commission in 2019. Figure 2b presents the number of concepts studied per paper. Among the reviewed works, Rasheed et al. [124] and Xiong et al. [172] explore the greatest number of concepts in depth, each covering 5 out of the 17 identified terms. When also considering concepts that are merely mentioned, Toreini et al. [151] stands out by addressing 9 out of the 17 concepts, more than any other paper in the set. In this paper, we aim to provide comprehensive coverage of all 17 concepts.

Figure 2: **Analysis of GoogleSearch results:** The label “Central” indicates that a concept was a central focus of the respective paper, while “Mentioned” refers to cases where the concept was briefly addressed, e.g., in a short paragraph or a single sentence. Note that many articles list several key concepts but concentrate only on a subset of them. If a term was merely included in such a list or not mentioned at all, it was excluded from the figure.

In the following, we will provide an overview of what we call the trustworthiness landscape, i.e., we will give tangible definitions of all of these terms and explain how they may contribute to the trustworthiness of a model. Thereby, we do uncover ambiguities in definitions as well as tensions and relatedness between them. Figure 4 offers a preliminary visualization of these connections. In this figure, terms are grouped according to their relevance to essentiality and justifiability, and further arranged to reflect content-related similarities. The rest of this manuscript is structured as follows: In Section 3.1, we start with a discussion of the most fundamental properties of an ML model, i.e., generalizability and closely related aspects such as performance, reliability, and robustness. Section 3.2 covers interpretability, explainability and cognates. In Section 3.3, we

(a) Publications per term.

(b) Publications per year

(c) ML publications in PubMed (1950-2024).

Figure 3: **Results of the PubMed query:** Figure 3a shows the number (y-axis) ML publications per term (x-axis) colored by the publication year. Whereas Figure 3b shows the articles per year between 2020 and 2024 (x-axis) colored by term. Figure 3c shows the ML publications with and without trustworthiness-related terms. We deliberately excluded ‘performance’ and ‘accuracy’ from plot 3a, 3b, and 3c, as these are evaluated in nearly all ML publications, which is also expected, since assessing some form of performance measure, such as accuracy, is a standard practice. Their presence would have dominated the entire plot, making it difficult to judge differences between other terms.

then expand the scope to the ML system level, which encompasses the ML model itself as well as surrounding components such as data collection and preprocessing pipelines, user interfaces, and other infrastructural elements (see Figure 5 for a depiction of the relationship between the ML model and the broader ML system). Within this Section, we discuss terms such as privacy, security, and confidentiality. Importantly, considerations regarding interference by malicious actors are mostly addressed in this Section. Lastly, we discuss auditability and accountability in Section 3.4 and conclude the manuscript with a view on tensions between all discussed concepts in Section 4.

Figure 4: **The trustworthiness landscape.** This figure illustrates the conceptual relationships among the concepts that we identify as relevant to the trustworthiness of machine learning. The edges represent connections that are discussed throughout the manuscript; however, other interpretations and connections may certainly be possible. The color coding reflects the relationship of each term to the two elements of our trustworthiness definition (essentiality and justifiability). Some properties, such as generalizability, performance, and reliability, are universally essential to ensure correct model functioning, whereas others may be essential for some tasks and depend more heavily on what is contextually justified from the trustor’s perspective in other tasks.

3.1 Performance, accuracy, generalizability, robustness, fairness and reliability

Currently, the existing body of ML methods is divided into four major realms each tailored to fulfilling a specific set of tasks: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning [132]. While we refer the interested reader to Sarker [132] for a thorough introduction to the specific challenges associated with each realm, we want to highlight what is common to all of them: they are designed to *perform* well for a specific task given experiences, i.e., a data set, to learn from. Thus, the question arises what constitutes a good performance at a specific task. In this paper, we focus on this question in the context of supervised learning since many real-world problems, in particular medical ones, can be broadly phrased as supervised learning tasks. However, many concepts and ideas discussed in the following have direct counterparts in the other realms or are transferable to them.

To understand what *performing well for a specific task* means, let us briefly recap key elements of supervised learning. In supervised learning, we are interested in approximating an unknown functional relationship $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ given a set of observed pairs $\{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)\}$, where $x_i \in \mathcal{X}$ is called the feature (or input) vector for a sample i and $y_i \in \mathcal{Y}$ the respective response (or output). More specifically, the task is to find the model \hat{f} that best approximates f . Depending on whether the values of \mathcal{Y} are continuous or discrete, we call this task regression or classification. We hypothesize that f belongs to a specific model type (hypothesis space) \mathcal{H} containing mappings $h : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$. We obtain \hat{f} by minimizing over some loss function $l : \mathcal{Y} \times \mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as an estimate of the empirical risk [68], i.e.,

$$R_{\text{emp}}(h) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N l(h(x_i), y_i) \quad (1)$$

and

$$\hat{f} = \operatorname{argmin}_h R_{\text{emp}}(h) \quad (2)$$

As can be seen in Equations (1) and (2), we are concerned with minimizing the loss, i.e., the deviation of a model output from the desired output and we say that *a model performs well* if the deviation is small. A typical loss function, also referred to as performance measure, for regression tasks is the mean-squared error (MSE) given as

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2, \quad (3)$$

which represents the average squared deviations of the true responses of the samples to the predicted values of the model. For classification, a commonly used metric is the accuracy, which is defined as the number of correct predictions T divided by the total number of samples N [55]:

$$\frac{T}{N} \quad (4)$$

We refer the interested reader to Naser and Alavi [110] for an overview of the diverse set of such performance measures and to Calster et al. [18] for guidelines on which measures to use in the medical domain for binary classification tasks. Which performance measure is appropriate for a specific task depends on a variety of factors, e.g., the type of the task and the properties of the data.

Figure 5: **Life cycle of an ML system.** This figure shows the life cycle of an ML system, which is broadly divided into two main phases: a training phase and a deployment phase. The training phase encompasses steps such as data collection, data preparation, ML model design, development, implementation, training and validation. The deployment phase covers ML inference, live system monitoring, and periodic audits or evaluations by relevant stakeholders.

3.1.1 Life cycle of an ML model

Independent of the task the ML model is designed for, it will cycle through several phases, i.e., a training phase, a validation phase, and a deployment phase (cf. Figure 5). During the first phase, i.e., the training phase, we can, as discussed above, optimize a performance measure since we know the true responses. Similarly, when we seek to validate our model on previously unseen data, for which we have an associated response, we can evaluate this (or another) performance measure once more. Indeed, this validation phase on unseen data with known responses serves the goal of estimating the *generalizability* of the model. When we say that a model generalizes well to unseen data, we mean that our model learns meaningful relationships of the data while discarding irrelevant information, e.g., measurement noise. Thus, it not only reflects or learns the training data but also the type of data and task we are interested in more generally. As a consequence, it should then also perform well when it is ultimately deployed in the real world, which is the goal of all ML training. Indeed, there is ample literature on the question of what renders a model generalizable [61], and we cannot discuss all of it within this review. Instead, we would like to focus on the three concepts reliability, robustness, and fairness since these are not only deeply woven with the properties that render a model generalizable [61, 173] but were also – potentially consequentially – identified as key features of trustworthiness within this review.

3.1.2 Data collection, bias and fairness

The basis of any ML model is the underlying data on which it is trained. Thus, ensuring the appropriateness of the data collection and subsequent processing procedure is paramount to obtaining high-quality ML models. But what does it mean for a data collection and processing procedure to be appropriate, and, if and how can we even mitigate issues arising from imperfect procedures? To answer these questions, we will discuss general data collection strategies, biases that they may incur, and what fairness of ML models often means in this context.

When we think about designing an ML model for a specific task, we implicitly consider which general type of data underlies this task and what our application scenario may look like. Theoretically, we can thus explicitly define all possible scenarios in which our ML model would finally be deployed and collect data, i.e., perform so-called *targeted data collection* [61]. While this may seem straightforward, it is practically impossible to achieve for sufficiently complex tasks such as those typically faced in medicine. Assume, for example, that we want to detect skin cancer from images of patient samples. In the formulation of the task, it is already stated that we need images of patients' skin lesions. However, we have to answer questions such as which cancer types our model should work on, which stages of cancer it should be able to detect, what kind of image data we should consider, which quality we need to have for these images, or how diverse the target population is (e.g., in terms of age, gender, and skin tone) [171]. Even if we could characterize our desired data sufficiently well, obtaining it may still be impossible in practice. For example, in our simple skin cancer case above, we can only collect data from patients who seek medical care. Moreover, our data will only comprise those patients who visit doctors participating in our data collection efforts and who consent to the use of their data in our ML model.

Thus, most likely, we will have to rely on some form of what is referred to as *passive data collection* by Heim et al. [61], i.e., samples are collected from an environment that cannot be controlled.

In the context of decision-making with ML methods, a suboptimal data collection strategy and even one that is considered optimal at the point in time the collection is performed can lead to *bias* within the data. In the following, we will discuss different biases that may occur throughout the ML modelling pipeline.

In Figure 6, we show five prominent types of biases, i.e., historical bias, representation bias, measurement bias, inductive bias, and evaluation bias, frequently discussed throughout the literature [32, 101, 146], along with the stages where they arise in the ML modelling pipeline. To begin with, the world that we live in has been shaped by its history. Thus, all data we can gather and all processes by which we gather data may reflect, at least to some extent, historical developments and existing social structures, including structural inequalities and injustices. Thus, there can be some form of bias, i.e., unwanted or inappropriate patterns in the data or the data gathering process, because of past events, which we refer to as historical bias. Note that this definition of historical bias is similar but not equivalent to the definition given in Suresh and Guttag [146], who restrict historical bias to unwanted or inappropriate patterns in the data. As a consequence of our historical bias definition, all subsequent biases are affected by and represent historical bias as well. However, by distinguishing these biases, we can understand if, where, and how to intervene to debias our ML models. We can see that already the way we sample our data from the true population in the real world (represented by $\mathcal{X}' \times \mathcal{Y}'$ in Figure 6), can incur representation bias. Suresh and Guttag [146] refer to bias introduced by the underrepresentation of a group (e.g., age, gender or ethnicity) in our input data as representation bias. This underrepresentation may not necessarily be caused by the selection strategy, such as specific preferences for sampling from particular groups within a population (known as selection bias [146]), but can also simply reflect the relative scarcity of certain group(s), e.g., arising because of historical reasons. Moreover, the population we may

Figure 6: **Biases within the ML modelling pipeline.** This figure visualizes where in the ML modeling pipeline bias can arise and how this affects the final ML model that we discover through training. Although not explicitly depicted in this figure, feedback loops occur because the predictions generated by the ML model are used to inform decisions by humans.

sample from may not be representative of the population we want to cast predictions for, e.g., because of geographic differences or changes in population over time. In our skin cancer example from above, our sampling strategy would prefer patients who regularly seek medical care from a physician participating in our study and consent to the use of their data, and, thus, our data would exhibit selection bias even though we did not intentionally focus on specific groups. In addition, it might happen that certain groups (e.g., children) are naturally underrepresented because they are more rarely affected by this disease, and, consequently, our data would be affected by additional representation bias due to this circumstance. After the collection of our data points, we must then measure meaningful input (features) and output (responses) characteristics of them. Unfortunately, it might often be barely achievable to measure ideal features and responses. Instead, we might only be able to measure (oversimplified) proxies, have different measurement devices across groups or varying resolution across groups. Thereby, we introduce measurement bias. In our example from above, we might rely on a physician’s assessment of the skin lesions to train our model. While this is clearly a sensible choice, the physician’s assessment of a skin lesion is only a proxy of the actual disease status of this skin lesion: for example, a patient may suffer from a very rare or as

yet unknown skin disease that appears similar to a specific skin cancer on images, and, thus, is misclassified by the physician. Moreover, it could be possible that the devices that the physician uses for diagnostics are more suitable for light skin than dark skin, introducing yet another layer of bias. Once we have measured the relevant features and responses of our data points, i.e., once we have generated the observed pairs $\{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)\}$, we can start the actual ML modelling part. Note that we conceptually include potential data (pre-)processing procedures in the modelling step of Figure 6. By choosing a hypothesis space \mathcal{H} , loss functions, and other properties of our ML algorithm, we may introduce inductive bias [69]. While there exist ML model classes that incur relatively little such bias, e.g., neural networks, others assume very strict relationships between the features and the responses, e.g., linear models, and, thus, exhibit higher inductive bias. Once the model is trained, it will typically be evaluated on internal test data sets or additional publicly available benchmarking data sets using performance metrics. We want to highlight here that focusing on single performance metrics or benchmark data sets can be highly deceptive, e.g., if particular groups are under-represented in the benchmark or the metric merely captures a specific aspect of a model. The choice of benchmark data sets and metrics depends on the world as it currently is, and thus, may be subject to the same biases that influenced our ML modelling pipeline from the outset. Suresh and Guttag [146] denote bias arising from the evaluation step as evaluation bias. The specific choice of evaluation data sets and metrics, together with our trained model, then influences not only how we will model our task within the next iteration but also how we sample from and measure the real world. Apart from that, the model and its results can have a profound impact on humans (in)directly being exposed to them, i.e., we create new historical bias in the feedback loop(s) from the evaluation to all other parts of the ML modelling pipeline.

Generally speaking, we would like to reduce the total bias in our pipeline to more accurately capture the real-world processes associated with our task. Given an already generated data set, bias mitigation strategies can be divided into three categories: (a) modification of the data set (pre-processing), (b) modification of the training procedure (in-processing), and (c) modification of the decisions after training (post-processing) [101, 9, 123]. Technically, these strategies, e.g., the modification of the training procedure, can introduce some form of bias to reduce the total bias within the ML pipeline. Which of the strategies is applicable and advisable depends on the task and the possibility to interfere with a particular ML model. Notably, Friedler et al. [43] point out that we should clearly document assumptions about the bias within our ML pipeline and, if, and how we aim to combat it.

A largely socially motivated subfield concerned with bias mitigation in the ML modelling pipeline is known as *fairness*. There exist various definitions of what constitutes fairness within the ML realm [71, 101, 9]. Broadly, fairness concerns avoidance of undue or arbitrary favoritism towards individuals or groups [101, 9]. Traditionally, many ML definitions of fairness involve some attribute of the individuals (most often a group membership) that is considered *sensitive* and that has been discriminated against historically [71, 9]. Examples of such attributes are gender, race, and age. Fairness definitions that use these group attributes then ensure some form of equal treatment of the groups by guaranteeing statistical properties of the outputs of the ML algorithm [101, 43]. For example, the equal opportunity definition states that the probability of being correctly assigned to the positive class should be equal across groups [59, 101]. Interestingly, a challenge with such group fairness notions is that they can lead to models treating individuals from different groups—who are otherwise similar—in markedly different ways. This can result in perceptions of unfairness at the individual level [36]. An alternative to such group fairness notions is *individual fairness*. Here, the overall idea is to assign similar outcomes to similar individuals given a socially fair or accepted similarity metric [36, 43]. It is important to note that it is often impossible to achieve different notions of fairness simultaneously [102, 43, 101]. For AI in medicine, such socially motivated no-

tions of fairness have to be used with caution, especially in personalized medicine where molecular data of patients is used to train models. If such a model performs poorly for an under-represented (social) group within the data this may indicate that there is a biological component involved that is not captured adequately by the model. Artificially rectifying this using fairness mechanisms does not generally account for this. Moreover, the incorporation of such fairness notions can reduce performance for more strongly represented groups. When the training and deployment populations align, this may lead to an overall increase in false predictions, which is highly undesirable in medical settings. A better alternative here would likely be to acknowledge the limitations of the model and to provide separate diagnosis, prognosis, or treatment routes for the affected patients. A research direction that increasingly gains traction, as it provides an alternative solution to the problems introduced by more classical and largely statistical fairness definitions, such as those discussed above, is *causal fairness* [97]. Instead of relying solely on the correlation of variables, ML models that realize causal fairness aim to represent the causal connection between the output and the attribute considered sensitive. This approach is particularly important in the medical domain: it is highly desirable that a model answers the question of why a specific diagnosis, prognosis or treatment should be performed (cf. our discussion on interpretability in Section 3.2). In addition, Binkyte et al. [14] et al. show that by distinguishing causal relationships from spurious correlations, causal fairness techniques can remove disparities without disrupting, or even increasing, the accuracy of the prediction. Overall, causal methods in the ML realm are usually based on the works of Pearl [119] or Rubin [127]. For an in-depth discussion of causal fairness notions, we refer the reader to Makhlof et al. [97].

Up to this point, our discussion has been focused on the fairness of the prediction. However, Grote and Keeling [52] argue that the ML prediction might not even be the (only) correct endpoint to assess fairness for AI in medicine, i.e., they claim that the correct endpoint is the final decision reached by the clinician in collaboration with the ML model and its prediction. This also implies that biases present in the human part of the decision process should be taken into account as well when assessing fairness. For instance, a bias in human decision-making may arise when a clinician scrutinizes AI-generated recommendations more rigorously for one group than another. Such a differential judgment of a prediction could stem from greater familiarity with the majority group. Another example would be that stereotypes override accurate predictions, such as when an algorithm correctly identifies breast cancer in a male patient or menopause in a younger woman, but the clinician dismisses the result due to preconceived notions. Such systematic under- or over-scrutiny of predictions across demographic groups can exacerbate disparities over time: when these decisions are fed back into the ML pipeline, they may reinforce existing biases, creating a feedback loop that perpetuates inequities in future predictions (cf. our discussion on historical bias).

3.1.3 Reliability

Within the ML realm, reliability is a concept with various different definitions and interpretations [61]. These definitions range from evaluation performance during the validation phase of an algorithm [61], over calibration of models [54], to certainty guarantees for single samples in the deployment phase via a procedure known as conformal prediction [80, 112, 113, 85]. Following a proposal by Heim et al. [61], we aim to present all these definitions using the IEEE standard computer dictionary definition translated into ML terminology as the underlying basis. The IEEE standard computer dictionary defines reliability as "the ability of a system or component to perform its required functions under stated conditions for a specified period of time." [1]. Heim et al. [61] deconstruct this definition into four elemental parts, i.e., (1) the system/component, (2) the correct functioning, (3) stated conditions, and (4) the time period. They then map these four parts in the

context of ML to (1) the ML model, (2) a failure/error model, (3) the data generating distribution, and (4) the deployment time, respectively. In summary, reliability can, thus, be defined as the ability of a model to function correctly (i.e., avoid failure) when making predictions on (new) data drawn from the same distribution as the training data.

Given such a definition, we can clearly see that the evaluation of performance measures on dedicated test set(s) during the validation phase serves the purpose of ensuring reliability. While we can reuse the same performance metrics from training during validation, it may also be beneficial to investigate additional ones to capture different aspects of model behavior [61]. Moreover, we may not only be interested in calculating aggregated performance measures over our complete test set but also in performances for specific subsets or even single instances that represent particularly critical use cases of our model. A thoroughly conducted evaluation may thus also help identify and subsequently also counteract biases introduced in the ML pipeline.

To understand reliability in terms of model calibration, we have to consider the probabilistic nature that ML models exhibit. Note that for simplicity, we restrict the following description to classification problems; however, similar theory is available for regression problems as well (cf. e.g. [56]). While Equation (2) implies that ML models directly learn a function that maps from the feature space to the output space, they often learn so-called predictive probabilities instead. More specifically, they learn the conditional probability $p(y|x)$, i.e., given instances in the feature space, they learn the probabilities of observing the different target values (classes in the case of classification). Given a (new) instance from the feature space, this predictive probability can then be used to derive an output value, i.e., the most probable one. Intuitively, we may consider a prediction with a high predictive probability, often also referred to as *confidence* or certainty of a model prediction, as a more reliable one. Underlying this intuition is the assumption that the predictive probability reflects the true probability of the event that is modelled. Unfortunately, this is not commonly guaranteed by ML procedures [114, 54]. The situation where the predictive probability does not reflect the true probability of the event that is modelled is denoted as *miscalibration*. Thus, the general goal of model calibration is to make models *reliable* in the sense that for any predictive probability it holds that the probability of the modelled event — conditioned on the given predictive probability — matches the predictive probability itself [78]. Assuming that $\hat{f}(x)$ models $p(y|x)$, we can mathematically express this as

$$\forall \hat{f}(x) : P(y|\hat{f}(x)) = \hat{f}(x) \tag{5}$$

which is also denoted as full or perfect calibration condition [107, 78]. To illustrate this, consider a binary classifier $\hat{f}(x)$ with predictive probabilities for the positive class as output. Suppose we collect all samples where the model predicts a probability of 0.8. If the model is perfectly calibrated, then among these samples, approximately 80% should actually belong to the positive class. In other words, the observed frequency of the positive class, conditioned on the model predicting 0.8, should be close to 0.8. Note that there are also weaker forms of (5), see Kirchenbauer et al. [78]. Similar to how we can assess the performance of a model in predicting output labels, we can also assess how well a model is calibrated [108, 54, 122]. Briefly, we measure the difference between the predictive probability and the observed frequency of the event, conditioned on that predictive probability. We refer the interested reader to Posocco and Bonnefoy [122] for an in-depth discussion on this topic, in particular, the most commonly used classification calibration metric, i.e., the expected calibration error (ECE). If one aims to counteract miscalibration, there exist mainly two alternative routes: either training calibrated models ab initio or post-hoc calibration of trained models [108]. While training calibrated models may restrict one to specific model classes (e.g., Bayesian neural networks [105, 81] or deep ensembles [81]) or the use of specific loss functions during optimization (e.g., focal loss [46]), post-hoc calibration is more versatile and often model-agnostic [61, 98]. This means that

post-hoc calibration methods typically require only access to the predictive probabilities, i.e., the model remains a black box, and then calibrate them. Thus, post-hoc calibration is often the more feasible alternative. Counterintuitively, even perfectly calibrated models do not necessarily lead to increased levels of trust of a human in a specific prediction [29, 160]. Therefore, other methods discussed below may be better suited to increase the trustworthiness of, and trust in, the system. As briefly mentioned above, the predictive probability is also often denoted as certainty of the prediction and as such, calibration methods can be related to the broader field of uncertainty quantification and representation methods, cf. [68]. In the following, we will discuss aspects of uncertainty quantification relevant to our manuscript. For a thorough introduction to uncertainty in ML, we refer the interested reader to Hüllermeier and Waegeman [68].

Generally, uncertainty quantification and the corresponding methods are related to both reliability and robustness, as we will see in the following sections. In this section, we would like to conclude with one last notion of reliability that is directly related to uncertainty quantification, i.e., uncertainty guarantees during the deployment phase via a specific class of methods known as conformal prediction (CP) [162, 135, 42, 4, 150]. CP is a versatile framework that can sit on top of almost any ML method, given that it provides a notion of predictive (un)certainty [4], e.g., the predictive probability. Given a user-specified desired certainty level, the CP framework takes the notion of uncertainty and converts it into a mathematically rigorous certainty guarantee exactly meeting the user-specified certainty level. More specifically, CP constructs sets of classes (classification) and intervals around point predictions (regression), which then contain the true (unknown) value with the desired certainty level. Hüllermeier and Waegeman [68] describe CP procedures as almost orthogonal to how calibration of predictive probabilities works. CP procedures define a desired (un)certainty level for the final predictions first, and then build statistically valid sets and intervals that meet the desired certainty level instead of trying to calibrate the predictive probability. Indeed, CP could also be described as a statistically sound post-hoc calibration of the predicted sets (classification) and intervals (regression) regardless of whether the predictive probabilities (that are required as input to CP procedures) are calibrated.

Clearly, both forms of uncertainty quantification and representation discussed in the previous paragraphs (calibration of predictive probabilities and CP) help assess when a model is likely to fail on data drawn from the same distribution as the training data. In doing so, they contribute to model reliability in a way that aligns with the IEEE definition. Overall, uncertainty quantification is essential for trustworthy AI, as understanding the limits of a model, specifically, whether and in what ways it is uncertain, enables us to better estimate the risks associated with relying on its decisions. However, since the final decision often rests with humans, particularly in high-stakes domains such as medicine, it is equally important to examine how these uncertainty quantification methods influence human decision-making. In recent years, a growing body of research has explored human-AI interaction using CP as an uncertainty quantification method [141, 30]. These studies generally suggest that such approaches hold promise for supporting human decision-making, although further investigation is needed to fully understand their impact and limitations [70]. For instance, the relationship between automation bias, i.e., the tendency of humans to overly rely on computer results, and CP requires further investigation and consideration.

3.1.4 Robustness

Like many of the terms discussed in this paper, the term *robustness* is not a monolithic concept in the literature but rather a set of related concepts that share some common overall meaning. In the following, we will discuss several of these concepts, i.e., perturbation robustness, adversarial robustness, and divergence robustness. Similar to how we conceptualized reliability within the ML

context based on its IEEE definition, we now adopt the IEEE definition of robustness as unifying concept for the different notions of robustness within the ML realm following the proposal by Heim et al. [61]. The IEEE states that robustness is "the degree to which a system or component can function correctly in the presence of invalid inputs or stressful environmental conditions." [1]. We can translate this in the ML context to the ability of a model to function properly (i.e., avoid failure) when making predictions on (new) data drawn from a distribution that differs from the training distribution. Thus, the key difference between reliability and robustness based on these definitions is whether the data to which the model is applied is in-distribution (reliability) or out-of-distribution (robustness). Indeed, traditional arguments about when models generalize have the underlying assumption that the deployment time data is drawn from the same distribution as the training data, i.e., the deployment data is in-distribution, cf., e.g., [22]. Moreover, training a model that generalizes to any out-of-distribution data without specific assumptions about the relationship between training and deployment data is impossible [34]. Thus, we have to explicitly model perturbations or distribution shifts in order to achieve generalization in such scenarios. Indeed, it is rather common that we would like to apply a trained model to out-of-distribution data: it might be impossible to gather data that truly reflects the population in the deployment scenario, unforeseen scenarios might arise, or the target population might change over time (cf. our discussion on bias during data collection). In addition, an ML system might be exposed to inputs crafted by a malicious agent that wants to exploit a system for personal benefit. An example of a common (benign) distribution shift in biology or medicine is known as batch effect [72, 137, 177, 154, 175]. Briefly, this is the technical variability of biological assays because of, e.g., experiment times, lab personnel, reagents, or instruments or even hospitals/sites at which the data is gathered [177]. Many traditional batch effect correction methods require explicit knowledge of batch membership or the availability of multiple instances from the same batch, and are, thus, not directly applicable to single new instances as we would typically encounter during the deployment time of an ML model [88, 175, 94]. Thus, the detection of out-of-distribution instances, the tolerance of (small) perturbations or shifts, and the direct modeling of certain distribution shifts within the ML learning algorithm is highly desirable for a model to function correctly within a deployment environment. In general, we hope that the predictive probability directly reflects when a new instance is out of the distribution of the training data, i.e., that it would be low in these cases. However, this is not generally the case, e.g., as illustrated by Nguyen et al. [111] or by Hein et al. [62]. However, numerous methods can help in detecting when instances deviate from the training distribution, e.g., similarity-based methods [99] or Bayesian methods [45]. For a comprehensive overview of such methods, we refer the reader to Yang et al. [174]. We could not only be interested in deciding whether a sample is out-of-distribution, but also make our model tolerant to specific perturbations or shifts. Methods that are categorized under the term *perturbation robustness* aim at making a model robust to small changes in the input, i.e., changes of the form $x' = x + \delta$, where δ is constrained in magnitude or structure (see e.g., [48, 161, 23]). Instead of simply minimizing the empirical risk as given in (1), we then minimize the risk under a specific set of allowed perturbations. This leads to a min-max type of optimization problem [163], where the objective is to find model parameters that minimize the maximum loss incurred among the set of allowable perturbations. In doing so, the model is trained to be robust against the most challenging variations within a defined perturbation class. Under specific conditions, e.g., constraining the perturbations to a radius ϵ , it is possible to guarantee perturbation robustness. Models that are proven to fulfil robustness are called *certified robust* [87, 96, 83, 26]. If the perturbations were crafted by a malicious agent, i.e., an adversary, with the intent to fool the model, robust optimization to defend against the adversary is also referred to with the term *adversarial robustness* [31, 48, 115, 51, 143, 155, 19]. Generally, a model is said to be *adversarially robust* if it can mitigate erroneous predictions for instances

specifically crafted by a malicious agent to fool it, i.e., adversarial robustness does not necessarily have to refer to the perturbation setting only, but – given this broad definition – can in principle relate to other robustness types as well. The final type of robustness we briefly address here is *divergence robustness*. This concept centers on modelling and mitigating distributional divergences between the training and deployment phases. Thus, in contrast to perturbation robustness, which is concerned with modelling variations for individual instances, divergence robustness shifts the focus to entire sets of instances and how these sets may change between training and deployment. Overall, there exist three main types of shifts: shifts in the feature space (covariate shifts), the conditional probability distribution of the response on the features (concept shifts), and shifts in the response labels (label or semantic shifts), cf. [61]. Often, ML models require information about the expected shift, e.g., in terms of prior knowledge or access to some deployment time data, to incorporate solution strategies into their inner workings [136, 38, 49]. However, it may be infeasible to obtain such knowledge or data beforehand; thus, there also exist strategies that try to estimate emerging distribution shifts ad hoc during deployment [130, 7, 176]. Generally, the field concerned with equipping models with means to combat distributional changes is broad [91]. Amongst others, it encompasses areas such as domain adaptation, transfer learning, meta-learning, and out-of-distribution generalization.

For many medical tasks that can be addressed using ML, ensuring some form of robustness is essential. This is due to the inherent challenges in biological and medical data, such as technical noise, variability across assays, differences between hospitals, and a changing population over time.

3.2 Interpretability, explainability, and cognates

Defining the terms interpretability, explainability, transparency, and their cognates has been an intricate quest within the ML community and across disciplines [90, 128, 79, 138, 84]. What generally unites these definitions is their shared focus on fostering different forms and degrees of human understanding of ML models, i.e., the aim to counteract their opacity. To relate the diverse terms to each other, a plethora of taxonomies have been proposed during the previous decade, e.g., [33, 47, 6, 84, 138]. While we refer the interested reader to Speith [138] for an in-depth review of the commonalities and differences between those taxonomies, we briefly explain some of the most prevalent terms. To this end, we will mostly rely on definitions as proposed in Speith [138] and Lenhof et al. [84]. Figure 7 provides a simplified overview of the taxonomy introduced by Speith [138], enriched with annotations that align with the conceptual distinctions discussed in Lenhof et al. [84].

Similar to Lipton [90], Lenhof et al. [84] argue that *interpretability* is the overarching term and relates to the general property of a model being understandable to a human realized by whatever means. The research field concerned with rendering models interpretable is, however, often called explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) (cf. Speith [138]), which is why *explainability* may be used interchangeably with *interpretability* in some cases. Methods that render models interpretable can be separated from each other in a lot of what Speith [138] calls dimensions, e.g., stage (post-hoc vs ante-hoc), scope (local vs global) or output format (speech, written text, images, etc.). We argue that the most fundamental of these dimensions is the stage dimension, which is also the one where most authors of taxonomies agree on in terms of definition [138]. Here, one distinguishes between inherent model interpretability/transparency (also referred to as ante-hoc explainability Speith [138]) and post-hoc explainability, i.e., explanations are added to a model after training. Usually, relatively simple models, e.g., decision trees or linear models, are regarded as inherently interpretable, while more complex models, such as deep neural networks, need post-hoc explanations to become more understandable to humans. As outlined by Lenhof et al. [84], however, simple

Figure 7: **Simplified taxonomy of interpretability/explainability methods.** This figure presents a simplified taxonomy of interpretability, adapted from Speith [138] and Lenhof et al. [84]. At the top level, it introduces the overarching concept, i.e., interpretability or explainability, two terms that are often used interchangeably. The middle layer differentiates key dimensions that help characterize interpretability methods, while the bottom layer provides representative instantiations of these dimensions. For clarity, relations between dimensions are omitted.

methods can also benefit from the addition of explainability layers.

Let us now investigate how interpretability and cognates relate to trustworthiness and the remaining trustworthiness-related properties. We argue that, in contrast to the previously discussed trustworthiness-related properties, interpretability and cognates are often less essential for a given task and more related to what is justified for the trustors, i.e., different stakeholders. Interestingly, in AI ethics literature, there is a contentious debate about whether interpretability should be an epistemic requirement or a basic ethical principle to be met by AI systems [28]. For instance, Kawamleh [76] argues against a substantial interpretability requirement in the context of medicine and healthcare, thus supporting our moderate claim in this regard. To understand our claim, let us investigate a simple example for decision support: An ML model might become trained to make a prediction of the therapeutic response of a patient to a particular drug, to decide whether it should be administered. The definition of *functioning properly* here clearly includes the capability of the model to make correct predictions. This would typically include a thorough performance evaluation under various considerations (such as robustness, generalizability, fairness, etc.) during the training phase, as well as the delivery of a prediction and an (assumed) reliability of that prediction at deployment time. However, simply making a recommendation does not need an explanation. Yet, it might still be justified for medical doctors or patients to understand the model’s reasoning. A medical doctor might, for example, have domain knowledge, which would help them reinforce a prediction or give a reason for intervention. A patient might feel more compliant with a therapy if they understand why it should work in their case. When taking into account the

fact that in many research fields, more complex models, in particular those based on deep neural networks, surpass simpler models in terms of performance, it seems thus warranted to opt for them and add explainability layers afterwards. The tradeoff that has to be made is also known as the interpretability-performance tradeoff [138]. Briefly speaking, when opting for a particular model, one has to keep in mind not only the performance but also the desired translucency [124] of the model (Speith [138] suggests the term fidelity for this). More specifically, one has to ask the question of how close one would like the explanations to the inner workings of the algorithm. While inherently interpretable models are fully translucent, any explanation added to a model afterwards will only reflect the model to some degree [128], and thus, less accurately reflect the underlying biology. In particular, in areas where there is no clear evidence for the superiority of complex models, we agree with Rudin [128] that inherently interpretable models should be the preferred choice. In a similar fashion, we may want to foster different forms of understanding depending on the trustor [139]. While we are convinced that lowest level of understanding in the hierarchy by Speith et al. [139], i.e., *recognizing* what the output of the model should be, should always be fulfilled by any model, the satisfaction of other forms of understanding such as *predicting* outcomes based on the explanations, may depend on the concrete application scenario. Note that inherently interpretable models will enable all of the different levels of understanding as defined by Speith et al. [139].

While we generally argue that interpretability is not necessarily indicative or a prerequisite of the correct functioning of an ML model, there are important exceptions, particularly in biological and medical contexts. Here, certain forms of interpretability (mostly concept-based ones, cf. Lenhof et al. [84]) should always be considered: at a minimum, models should not contradict well-established biological knowledge, and if such contradictions do occur, they must be investigated with particular care.

3.3 Misuse throughout the life cycle of an ML system

Within the previous sections, we primarily focused on trustworthiness-related properties of the ML model itself, specifically for its training methodology and evaluation strategies. However, in practical applications, an ML model is typically embedded within a broader system as already indicated in Figure 5. This system encompasses components such as data collection and preprocessing pipelines, user interfaces, and other infrastructural elements that collectively shape the usability and effectiveness of the model in practice. We refer to this integrated setup as the ML system, in contrast to the ML model as a (core) component. In the following discussion on the trustworthiness-related properties of privacy, security, safety, confidentiality, and integrity, we shift our attention from the ML model to the entire system.

As indicated in Section 3.1.1, an ML system repeatedly cycles through several phases during its lifespan (cf. Figure 5). Throughout this process, the components of the ML system (including the physical entities underlying the system as well as the interface that users employ to interact with the ML model) are vulnerable to (un)intentional misuse, which may compromise the correct functioning of the entire system. In particular, the misuse may affect the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of the ML system [117, 172], which are the three fundamental pillars of the classical information security framework [131, 140]. Here, confidentiality refers to two key objectives: (a) the protection of any sensitive information, e.g., the architecture and parameters of the model as well as the underlying data, from unauthorized access while (b) enabling individuals to retain control over their private data, including how they are used and shared, which is also referred to as privacy goal [140]. Integrity covers the concepts of (a) data integrity, which ensures that data is only changed in a specified and authorized manner, and (b) system integrity to ensure that the intended operation of the system remains unaltered without being compromised by intentional or accidental

Figure 8: **Dimensions that define an attack.** This figure visualizes how we can characterize an attack(er).

unauthorized interference [140]. Lastly, availability requires that the system and its outputs are reliably and promptly accessible to authorized users [140].

Depending on whether the misuse of the system is intentional or unintentional, the misuse is typically referred to as a security problem (intentional misuse) or safety problem (unintentional / accidental misuse). Notably, we can directly relate safety and security to the IEEE definitions of reliability and robustness as provided in the previous sections: On the one hand, the fulfillment of reliability necessitates the correct functioning of the system during the deployment time when a user interacts with it in the intended way, and thus, typically, will encompass techniques to mitigate unintentional misuse of the system, e.g., through real-world test runs before deployment as well as user guidelines. On the other hand, the fulfillment of robustness will entail specific countermeasures against failure under stressful conditions. These stressful conditions can either stem from unexpected user behaviour, e.g., edge cases that have not been encountered during real-world test runs, or specific attacks from malicious agents trying to exploit parts of the system, which are known as adversarial attacks (cf. Subsection 3.1.4). General measures to limit failure under stressful conditions may include a system design that handles unexpected events with sensible default settings, as well as logging and monitoring services that facilitate the detection and analysis of such unexpected events. In particular, such logging and monitoring facilities should help in performing regular audits of the ML system. In addition to these general measures, there should be mechanisms in place that defend against specific attacks. For comprehensive overviews of attacks and defense mechanisms, we refer the interested reader to Papernot et al. [117], Tabassi et al. [148], Liu et al. [92], Chakraborty et al. [20], Wu et al. [170], while we provide a brief overview in the following. In addition, we will highlight specific attacks as well as security issues more generally that may be encountered in research settings within the medical domain.

Generally, an attack can be characterized by the attacker’s goal, the target, the used technique, and the attacker’s knowledge about and capabilities to interfere with the target [117, 148] (cf. Figure 8). Within the context of this paper, the target is the ML system. Here, it is instructive to further explicitly distinguish between the ML model and all other components of the system as putative targets since the model constitutes the part of the system that differentiates it from others. Consequently, the ML model (including the interaction of the model with all other com-

ponents) is often the primary focus of novel attack and defense mechanisms. While the specific goals of an attack may vary, the overarching goal can be described as the pursuit of some form of advantage for the attacker and will most often fall under breaches of one of the three fundamental pillars of the classical information security framework introduced above. How well this goal can be achieved depends on the knowledge and capabilities of the attacker: some attackers might have knowledge about and access to the entire system (referred to as *white box adversaries* [117]) and will, thus, be able to launch extremely devastating attacks. Other attackers will only have limited knowledge and access to the system. In extreme cases, a so-called black box adversary might only have access to the responses provided by the system. Yet, black-box adversaries can still leverage the system outputs as an oracle to reconstruct a surrogate model that may serve various purposes [147, 116, 109]. Thus, the knowledge and capabilities of the adversary also limit the range of techniques available to achieve a specific goal. Clearly, oracle attacks can be executed by virtually all adversaries. Other attacks, e.g., poisoning attacks, where a malicious agent injects altered training data into the ML model, require at least partial access to the system [39]. Within the ML domain, adversarial techniques are often distinguished based on the stage of the life cycle where they are employed [117, 148]. Most notably, training-level techniques (e.g., poisoning) are distinguished from deployment-level techniques (e.g., oracle attacks). Similarly, the defenses against these attacks are often classified using a similar taxonomy (cf. [117, 148]). Interestingly, the defense against poisoning often involves the same methodological approaches that we already encountered within our discussion on robustness (cf. Subsection 3.1.4), especially out-of-distribution detection, perturbation robustness and divergence robustness. Moreover, a model that is robust to distributional changes may also be better suited to preserve the privacy of individuals. Indeed, there is a direct connection between (adversarial) robustness and differential privacy (DP) [35, 121, 83], a form of privacy that ensures that the presence or absence of a single example in a data set must not significantly change the output of the model [16]. Due to its theoretical privacy guarantees, quantifiable protection level, and robustness to post-processing, DP is often referred to as the gold standard of privacy protection. The invariance to post-processing is particularly important in ML because it guarantees that any model learned from the DP-obfuscated data will worsen its privacy. Despite its benefits, differential privacy’s accuracy trade-off is often too severe for medical applications, which is why its use in this domain is currently limited [93]. Another privacy-preserving strategy is the use of *homomorphic encryption* (HE). HE is a form of encryption that allows computations to be performed directly on encrypted data. When the result is decrypted, it matches the outcome that would have been obtained if the same computation had been carried out on the raw data. This scheme enables training or inference with ML models without exposing the underlying sensitive information [2] and is increasingly adopted for biomedical tasks [169]. Another technique to preserve data privacy is called *federated learning* (FL). Here, the key idea is to collaboratively train a global model without sharing the raw (sensitive) data [86]. Typically, each participant can download a model for training and sends updates, e.g., gradients or weight updates, to a global server. An averaged update over all participants is then used as new global model, i.e., the global model was never directly exposed to the sensitive data. However, both HE and FL have limitations: HE incurs computational overhead and supports only limited operations, while FL may, e.g., still leak information through shared model updates unless enhanced with other techniques [64]. For instance, the combination of FL with the aforementioned DP has gained growing interest, as applying DP to local updates helps mitigate the risk of unintended information leakage [44].

While some defense techniques need to be directly integrated into the ML model itself, others may rather be implemented at the system level and include classical information security strategies, such as blacklist-based approaches for sanitizing in- or output during deployment. Although several of the security mechanisms sit on top of the ML model and do not directly alter the ML

model, they are nevertheless essential to ensure the correct functioning of the entire system, i.e., to ensure trustworthiness. In particular, attacks against the integrity and availability pillar would lead to a malfunctioning or unavailable system, respectively, if not defended against. To what extent privacy-preserving measures must be implemented strongly depends on the application case. For many real-world biomedical applications, there are strict legal requirements to guarantee the protection of sensitive or personal patient data while simultaneously granting authorized individuals (complete) access. Notably, even making the underlying trained ML model publicly available may be problematic since information about individuals might be leaked. According to Feldman [40], in some situations, there might even be a need to memorize specific data points to enable generalization and these memorized data points may then become revealed to malicious parties. For many research questions that employ publicly available data to train models, e.g., as encountered when working on model systems such as cell lines (cf. [85, 17]), there is little need to apply privacy-preserving techniques since no private data is involved. However, especially robustness-related techniques may still be important to apply in order to combat distributional divergences that commonly occur within this domain (cf. our discussion on robustness in Subsection 3.1.4).

3.4 Auditability and Accountability

Generally, auditability refers to the property of a system that ensures that it can be investigated and assessed by designated parties [151]. From this definition, it follows that (a) the system must retain enough information, e.g., through logging and monitoring facilities, to allow for meaningful inspection and (b) the system must be accessible to authorized parties in ways that allow oversight, even when internal mechanisms are otherwise opaque, without compromising specific security or privacy requirements. In the context of AI/ML, auditability must also be a property of the underlying ML model [103], since otherwise the core component of the system, i.e., the model itself, cannot be properly investigated. We argue that in many scenarios, all trustworthiness-related properties discussed in this manuscript, including, but not limited to, fairness, reliability, robustness, interpretability, security, and privacy, should be systematically evaluated as part of the audit process. This approach enables audits to capture both technical performance and alignment with ethical standards and legal requirements. Closely related to the concept of auditability is the concept of (software) traceability, which is a property of a system that allows the establishment of (causal) link chains between system components [3]. For ML systems, it is particularly interesting to trace system outputs back to specific inputs, processes, or actors. Traceability is essential for reconstructing the (causal) chain behind model behaviour and is, thus, often a prerequisite for effective auditing and identification of actors or processes responsible for certain outputs. Building on auditability and traceability, accountability ensures that the question of who should be held responsible for system outputs and under what conditions can be addressed [27, 124]. Clearly, for accountability to be actionable, the system must be auditable (and traceable) so that investigations can be conducted effectively.

Together, auditability, traceability, and accountability contribute to the transparency of the entire ML system. However, it is important to recognize that these three concepts and, thus, ML system transparency as such, may be at odds with certain security and privacy-preserving strategies, requiring careful trade-offs in system design. For example, enabling auditability (and traceability) requires logging and data retention, which can conflict with privacy-preserving principles such as data minimization and user anonymity. Similarly, providing access for oversight may expose internal system details, creating conflicts with security strategies aimed at protecting confidentiality and increasing the risk of adversarial manipulation.

In most research settings, auditability and accountability play only a minor role, as models are

Figure 9: **Key tensions between concepts discussed in this manuscript.** This figure visualizes the tensions between trustworthiness-related concepts that we describe within this manuscript. A more complete overview of the relationships is shown in Figure 4.

mainly used for exploratory purposes and are not subject to strict regulatory requirements. Nevertheless, well-documented studies remain justified to enable the reproducibility of the presented work, which should ultimately foster trust in science based on AI. In contrast, in real-world medical applications, auditability and accountability are not only required for the trustor to justifiably believe that the system functions properly, but may also be considered essential for proper system functioning, particularly in terms of safety considerations of the ML system.

4 Conclusion

In our manuscript, we thoroughly investigated the following 17 concepts identified during our initial literature search: *robustness*, *fairness*, *interpretability/explainability*, *privacy*, *security*, *transparency*, *safety*, *accountability*, *integrity*, *confidentiality*, *generalizability*, *reliability*, *performance*, *accuracy*, *confidence*, *translucency*, and *auditability*. Moreover, we supplemented these with additional concepts such as *bias (mitigation)*, *availability*, or *traceability* if required to contextualize connections between concepts better. Our analysis revealed that many of the discussed concepts lack universally accepted definitions. Instead, they represent clusters of related ideas that are often used intuitively across the literature. Where appropriate, our manuscript unifies these ideas and provides tangible and operationalizable definitions that support their practical implementation

and evaluation. Moreover, we noted that the terms *reliability*, *robustness*, and *transparency* are employed with distinct meanings depending on context, i.e., whether used at the ML model level (cf. Sub-Sections 3.1.3 and 3.1.4, and Section 3.2) or the broader ML system level (cf. Sections 3.3 and 3.4).

In addition, many of the connections between concepts discussed in this manuscript are characterized by tensions (see Figure 9 for an overview), often requiring domain-specific trade-offs to be considered. Performance, in particular, frequently lies at the center of these tensions: efforts to enhance privacy, fairness, or interpretability, for instance, may come at the cost of reduced performance. While our analysis is situated within the context of ML for medicine and life science research, where some considerations may be less important, priorities can shift significantly in real-world medical decision-making or in other application domains. We argue that our gradual assignment of these concepts to the two elements of our trustworthiness definition (essentiality and justifiability) reflects this complexity: some properties, such as generalizability, performance, and reliability, are universally essential to ensure correct model functioning, whereas others may be essential for some tasks and depend more heavily on what is contextually justified from the trustor’s perspective in other tasks. Ultimately, we believe that our work supports practitioners and researchers by clarifying the conceptual trustworthiness landscape in ML, highlighting critical tensions between key concepts, and offering a framework to guide the development and deployment of trustworthy AI systems, particularly in the medical domain.

Acknowledgments

This work is partially supported by the Ministry of Science and Culture of Lower Saxony through funds from the program *zukunft.niedersachsen* of the Volkswagen Foundation for the ‘CAIMed – Lower Saxony Center for Artificial Intelligence and Causal Methods in Medicine’ project (grant no. ZN4257).

L.-M. R. and A.V. performed this work in the context of the European RADAR project and have received funding from the European Union’s Horizon program under grant agreement No. 101178148. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The authors thank Lena Kästner for her thoughtful input on questions of AI trustworthiness.

References

- [1] Ieee standard glossary of software engineering terminology. *IEEE Std 610.12-1990*, pages 1–84, 1990. doi: 10.1109/IEEESTD.1990.101064.
- [2] Abbas Acar, Hidayet Aksu, A Selcuk Uluagac, and Mauro Conti. A survey on homomorphic encryption schemes: Theory and implementation. *ACM Computing Surveys (Csur)*, 51(4): 1–35, 2018.
- [3] Nouf Alturayef, Jameleddine Hassine, and Irfan Ahmad. Machine learning approaches for automated software traceability: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Systems and Software*, page 112536, 2025.
- [4] Anastasios N Angelopoulos, Stephen Bates, et al. Conformal prediction: A gentle introduction. *Foundations and trends® in machine learning*, 16(4):494–591, 2023.

- [5] Reiner Anselm, Gunnar Duttge, Volker Lipp, Friedemann Nauck, and Silke Schicktanz. *Autonomie und Vertrauen: Schlüsselbegriffe der modernen Medizin*. Springer-Verlag, 2015.
- [6] Alejandro Barredo Arrieta, Natalia Díaz-Rodríguez, Javier Del Ser, Adrien Bennetot, Siham Tabik, Alberto Barbado, Salvador García, Sergio Gil-López, Daniel Molina, Richard Benjamins, et al. Explainable artificial intelligence (xai): Concepts, taxonomies, opportunities and challenges toward responsible ai. *Information fusion*, 58:82–115, 2020.
- [7] Yong Bai, Yu-Jie Zhang, Peng Zhao, Masashi Sugiyama, and Zhi-Hua Zhou. Adapting to online label shift with provable guarantees. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35:29960–29974, 2022.
- [8] Annette Baier. Trust and antitrust. *ethics*, 96(2):231–260, 1986.
- [9] Solon Barocas, Moritz Hardt, and Arvind Narayanan. *Fairness and machine learning: Limitations and opportunities*. MIT press, 2023.
- [10] Firas Bayram and Bestoun S Ahmed. Towards trustworthy machine learning in production: An overview of the robustness in mlops approach. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 57(5):1–35, 2025.
- [11] Andreas Bender, Nadine Schneider, Marwin Segler, W Patrick Walters, Ola Engkvist, and Tiago Rodrigues. Evaluation guidelines for machine learning tools in the chemical sciences. *Nature Reviews Chemistry*, 6(6):428–442, 2022.
- [12] Emily M Bender, Timnit Gebru, Angelina McMillan-Major, and Shmargaret Shmitchell. On the dangers of stochastic parrots: Can language models be too big? In *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*, pages 610–623, 2021.
- [13] Tamay Besiroglu, Sage Andrus Bergerson, Amelia Michael, Lennart Heim, Xueyun Luo, and Neil Thompson. The compute divide in machine learning: A threat to academic contribution and scrutiny? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.02452*, 2024.
- [14] Ruta Binkyte, Ivaxi Sheth, Zhijing Jin, Mohammad Havaei, Bernhard Schölkopf, and Mario Fritz. Causality is key to understand and balance multiple goals in trustworthy ml and foundation models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.21123*, 2025.
- [15] Sara Blanco. Human trust in ai: a relationship beyond reliance. *AI and Ethics*, pages 1–14, 2025.
- [16] Alberto Blanco-Justicia, David Sánchez, Josep Domingo-Ferrer, and Krishnamurty Muralidhar. A critical review on the use (and misuse) of differential privacy in machine learning. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(8):1–16, 2022.
- [17] Jannis Born, Greta Markert, Nikita Janakaraman, Talia B Kimber, Andrea Volkamer, María Rodríguez Martínez, and Matteo Manica. Chemical representation learning for toxicity prediction. *Digital Discovery*, 2(3):674–691, 2023.
- [18] Ben Van Calster, Gary S. Collins, Andrew J. Vickers, Laure Wynants, Kathleen F. Kerr, Lasai Barreñada, Gael Varoquaux, Karandeep Singh, Karel G. M. Moons, Tina Hernandez-boussard, Dirk Timmerman, David J. McLernon, Maarten Van Smeden, and Ewout W. Steyerberg. Performance evaluation of predictive ai models to support medical decisions: Overview and guidance, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.10288>.

- [19] Nicholas Carlini, Anish Athalye, Nicolas Papernot, Wieland Brendel, Jonas Rauber, Dimitris Tsipras, Ian Goodfellow, Aleksander Madry, and Alexey Kurakin. On evaluating adversarial robustness. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1902.06705*, 2019.
- [20] Anirban Chakraborty, Manaar Alam, Vishal Dey, Anupam Chattopadhyay, and Debdeep Mukhopadhyay. A survey on adversarial attacks and defences. *CAAI Transactions on Intelligence Technology*, 6(1):25–45, 2021.
- [21] Chelsea Chandler, Peter W Foltz, and Brita Elvevåg. Using machine learning in psychiatry: the need to establish a framework that nurtures trustworthiness. *Schizophrenia bulletin*, 46(1):11–14, 2020.
- [22] Olivier Chapelle, Bernhard Scholkopf, and Alexander Zien. Semi-supervised learning. 2006. *Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press View Article*, 2, 2006.
- [23] Hongge Chen, Huan Zhang, Duane Boning, and Cho-Jui Hsieh. Robust decision trees against adversarial examples. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 1122–1131. PMLR, 2019.
- [24] Steven Cho, Seaton Cousins-Baxter, Stefano Ruberto, and Valerio Terragni. Automated trustworthiness testing for machine learning classifiers. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.05251*, 2024.
- [25] Mark Coeckelbergh. Can we trust robots? *Ethics and information technology*, 14(1):53–60, 2012.
- [26] Jeremy Cohen, Elan Rosenfeld, and Zico Kolter. Certified adversarial robustness via randomized smoothing. In Kamalika Chaudhuri and Ruslan Salakhutdinov, editors, *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Machine Learning*, volume 97 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pages 1310–1320. PMLR, 09–15 Jun 2019. URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v97/cohen19c.html>.
- [27] A Feder Cooper, Emanuel Moss, Benjamin Laufer, and Helen Nissenbaum. Accountability in an algorithmic society: relationality, responsibility, and robustness in machine learning. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*, pages 864–876, 2022.
- [28] João Figueiredo Nobre Brito Cortese, Fabio Gagliardi Cozman, Marcos Paulo Lucca-Silveira, and Adriano Figueiredo Bechara. Should explainability be a fifth ethical principle in ai ethics? *AI and Ethics*, 3(1):123–134, 2023.
- [29] Nina Corvelo Benz and Manuel Rodriguez. Human-aligned calibration for ai-assisted decision making. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36:14609–14636, 2023.
- [30] Jesse C Cresswell, Yi Sui, Bhargava Kumar, and Noël Vouitsis. Conformal prediction sets improve human decision making. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.13744*, 2024.
- [31] Nilesh Dalvi, Pedro Domingos, Mausam, Sumit Sanghai, and Deepak Verma. Adversarial classification. In *Proceedings of the tenth ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, pages 99–108, 2004.
- [32] David Danks and Alex John London. Algorithmic bias in autonomous systems. In *Ijcai*, volume 17, pages 4691–4697, 2017.

- [33] Saikat Das, Namita Agarwal, Deepak Venugopal, Frederick T Sheldon, and Sajjan Shiva. Taxonomy and survey of interpretable machine learning method. In *2020 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, pages 670–677. IEEE, 2020.
- [34] Shai Ben David, Tyler Lu, Teresa Luu, and Dávid Pál. Impossibility theorems for domain adaptation. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pages 129–136. JMLR Workshop and Conference Proceedings, 2010.
- [35] Cynthia Dwork. Differential privacy. In *International colloquium on automata, languages, and programming*, pages 1–12. Springer, 2006.
- [36] Cynthia Dwork, Moritz Hardt, Toniann Pitassi, Omer Reingold, and Richard Zemel. Fairness through awareness. In *Proceedings of the 3rd innovations in theoretical computer science conference*, pages 214–226, 2012.
- [37] Lea Eckhart, Kerstin Lenhof, Lisa-Marie Rolli, and Hans-Peter Lenhof. A comprehensive benchmarking of machine learning algorithms and dimensionality reduction methods for drug sensitivity prediction. *Briefings in bioinformatics*, 25(4), 2024.
- [38] Charles Elkan. The foundations of cost-sensitive learning. In *International joint conference on artificial intelligence*, volume 17, pages 973–978. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Ltd, 2001.
- [39] Birhanu Eshete. Making machine learning trustworthy. *Science*, 373(6556):743–744, 2021.
- [40] Vitaly Feldman. Does learning require memorization? a short tale about a long tail. In *Proceedings of the 52nd annual ACM SIGACT symposium on theory of computing*, pages 954–959, 2020.
- [41] Tiantian Feng, Rajat Hebbar, Nicholas Mehlman, Xuan Shi, Aditya Kommineni, Shrikanth Narayanan, et al. A review of speech-centric trustworthy machine learning: Privacy, safety, and fairness. *APSIPA Transactions on Signal and Information Processing*, 12(3), 2023.
- [42] Matteo Fontana, Gianluca Zeni, and Simone Vantini. Conformal prediction: a unified review of theory and new challenges. *Bernoulli*, 29(1):1–23, 2023.
- [43] Sorelle A Friedler, Carlos Scheidegger, and Suresh Venkatasubramanian. The (im) possibility of fairness: Different value systems require different mechanisms for fair decision making. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(4):136–143, 2021.
- [44] Jie Fu, Yuan Hong, Xinpeng Ling, Leixia Wang, Xun Ran, Zhiyu Sun, Wendy Hui Wang, Zhili Chen, and Yang Cao. Differentially private federated learning: A systematic review. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.08299*, 2024.
- [45] Yarín Gal and Zoubin Ghahramani. Dropout as a bayesian approximation: Representing model uncertainty in deep learning. In *international conference on machine learning*, pages 1050–1059. PMLR, 2016.
- [46] Arindam Ghosh, Thomas Schaaf, and Matthew Gormley. Adafocal: Calibration-aware adaptive focal loss. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35:1583–1595, 2022.
- [47] Leilani H Gilpin, David Bau, Ben Z Yuan, Ayesha Bajwa, Michael Specter, and Lalana Kagal. Explaining explanations: An overview of interpretability of machine learning. In *2018 IEEE 5th International Conference on data science and advanced analytics (DSAA)*, pages 80–89. IEEE, 2018.

- [48] Ian J Goodfellow, Jonathon Shlens, and Christian Szegedy. Explaining and harnessing adversarial examples. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6572*, 2014.
- [49] Arthur Gretton, Alex Smola, Jiayuan Huang, Marcel Schmittfull, Karsten Borgwardt, Bernhard Schölkopf, et al. Covariate shift by kernel mean matching. *Dataset shift in machine learning*, 3(4):5, 2009.
- [50] Léo Grinsztajn, Edouard Oyallon, and Gaël Varoquaux. Why do tree-based models still outperform deep learning on typical tabular data? *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 35:507–520, 2022.
- [51] Kathrin Grosse, Praveen Manoharan, Nicolas Papernot, Michael Backes, and Patrick McDaniel. On the (statistical) detection of adversarial examples. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.06280*, 2017.
- [52] Thomas Grote and Geoff Keeling. Enabling fairness in healthcare through machine learning. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 24(3):39, 2022.
- [53] Odd Erik Gundersen and Sigbjørn Kjensmo. State of the art: Reproducibility in artificial intelligence. In *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*, volume 32, 2018.
- [54] Chuan Guo, Geoff Pleiss, Yu Sun, and Kilian Q Weinberger. On calibration of modern neural networks. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 1321–1330. PMLR, 2017.
- [55] Ankur Gupta, Rohit Anand, Nidhi Sindhvani, Manisha Mittal, and Aman Dahiya. Performance and accuracy enhancement of machine learning & iot-based agriculture precision ai system. *SN Computer Science*, 5(7):930, 2024.
- [56] Fredrik K Gustafsson, Martin Danelljan, Goutam Bhat, and Thomas B Schön. Energy-based models for deep probabilistic regression. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 325–343. Springer, 2020.
- [57] Bo Han, Jiangchao Yao, Tongliang Liu, Bo Li, Sanmi Koyejo, Feng Liu, et al. Trustworthy machine learning: From data to models. *Foundations and Trends® in Privacy and Security*, 7(2-3):74–246, 2025.
- [58] PA Hancock, Theresa T Kessler, Alexandra D Kaplan, Kimberly Stowers, J Christopher Brill, Deborah R Billings, Kristin E Schaefer, and James L Szalma. How and why humans trust: A meta-analysis and elaborated model. *Frontiers in psychology*, 14:1081086, 2023.
- [59] Moritz Hardt, Eric Price, and Nati Srebro. Equality of opportunity in supervised learning. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 29, 2016.
- [60] Sascha Hauke, Sebastian Biedermann, Max Mühlhäuser, and Dominik Heider. On the application of supervised machine learning to trustworthiness assessment. In *2013 12th IEEE International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications*, pages 525–534. IEEE, 2013.
- [61] Eric Heim, Oren Wright, and David Shriver. A guide to failure in machine learning: Reliability and robustness from foundations to practice. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.00563*, 2025.

- [62] Matthias Hein, Maksym Andriushchenko, and Julian Bitterwolf. Why relu networks yield high-confidence predictions far away from the training data and how to mitigate the problem. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 41–50, 2019.
- [63] Hendrik Heuer and Andreas Breiter. More than accuracy: towards trustworthy machine learning interfaces for object recognition. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*, pages 298–302, 2020.
- [64] Kai Hu, Sheng Gong, Qi Zhang, Chaowen Seng, Min Xia, and Shanshan Jiang. An overview of implementing security and privacy in federated learning. *Artificial intelligence review*, 57(8):204, 2024.
- [65] Mengdi Huai. Fostering trustworthiness in machine learning algorithms. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, volume 38, pages 22670–22670, 2024.
- [66] Yue Huang, Lichao Sun, Haoran Wang, Siyuan Wu, Qihui Zhang, Yuan Li, Chujie Gao, Yixin Huang, Wenhan Lyu, Yixuan Zhang, et al. Position: Trustllm: Trustworthiness in large language models. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 20166–20270. PMLR, 2024.
- [67] Alberto Huertas Celdran, Jan Kreischer, Melike Demirci, Joel Leupp, Pedro Miguel Sánchez Sánchez, Muriel Figueredo Franco, Gerome Bovet, Gregorio Martinez Perez, and Burkhard Stiller. A framework quantifying trustworthiness of supervised machine and deep learning models. In *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, number 3381, pages 1–14. CEUR-WS, 2023.
- [68] Eyke Hullermeier and Willem Waegeman. Aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty in machine learning: An introduction to concepts and methods. *Machine learning*, 110(3):457–506, 2021.
- [69] Eyke Hullermeier, Thomas Fober, and Marco Mernberger. Inductive bias. In *Encyclopedia of systems biology*, pages 1018–1018. Springer, 2013.
- [70] Jessica Hullman, Yifan Wu, Dawei Xie, Ziyang Guo, and Andrew Gelman. Conformal prediction and human decision making. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.11709*, 2025.
- [71] Ben Hutchinson and Margaret Mitchell. 50 years of test (un) fairness: Lessons for machine learning. In *Proceedings of the conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*, pages 49–58, 2019.
- [72] W Evan Johnson, Cheng Li, and Ariel Rabinovic. Adjusting batch effects in microarray expression data using empirical bayes methods. *Biostatistics*, 8(1):118–127, 2007.
- [73] Jared Kaplan, Sam McCandlish, Tom Henighan, Tom B Brown, Benjamin Chess, Rewon Child, Scott Gray, Alec Radford, Jeffrey Wu, and Dario Amodei. Scaling laws for neural language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2001.08361*, 2020.
- [74] Sayash Kapoor and Arvind Narayanan. Leakage and the reproducibility crisis in machine-learning-based science. *Patterns*, 4(9), 2023.
- [75] Lena Kastner, Markus Langer, Veronika Lazar, Astrid Schomacker, Timo Speith, and Sarah Sterz. On the relation of trust and explainability: Why to engineer for trustworthiness.

- In *2021 IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW)*, pages 169–175. IEEE, 2021.
- [76] Suzanne Kawamleh. Against explainability requirements for ethical artificial intelligence in health care. *AI and Ethics*, 3(3):901–916, 2023.
- [77] Mohamed Kentour and Joan Lu. Analysis of trustworthiness in machine learning and deep learning. 2021.
- [78] John Kirchenbauer, Jacob Oaks, and Eric Heim. What is your metric telling you? evaluating classifier calibration under context-specific definitions of reliability. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.11454*, 2022.
- [79] Maya Krishnan. Against interpretability: a critical examination of the interpretability problem in machine learning. *Philosophy & Technology*, 33(3):487–502, 2020.
- [80] Matjaž Kukar and Igor Kononenko. Reliable classifications with machine learning. In *Machine Learning: ECML 2002: 13th European Conference on Machine Learning Helsinki, Finland, August 19–23, 2002 Proceedings 13*, pages 219–231. Springer, 2002.
- [81] Balaji Lakshminarayanan, Alexander Pritzel, and Charles Blundell. Simple and scalable predictive uncertainty estimation using deep ensembles. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 30, 2017.
- [82] Nancy K Lankton, D Harrison McKnight, and John Tripp. Technology, humanness, and trust: Rethinking trust in technology. *Journal of the association for information systems*, 16(10):1, 2015.
- [83] Mathias Lecuyer, Vaggelis Atlidakis, Roxana Geambasu, Daniel Hsu, and Suman Jana. Certified robustness to adversarial examples with differential privacy. In *2019 IEEE symposium on security and privacy (SP)*, pages 656–672. IEEE, 2019.
- [84] Kerstin Lenhof, Lea Eckhart, Lisa-Marie Rolli, and Hans-Peter Lenhof. Trust me if you can: a survey on reliability and interpretability of machine learning approaches for drug sensitivity prediction in cancer. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 25(5), 2024.
- [85] Kerstin Lenhof, Lea Eckhart, Lisa-Marie Rolli, Andrea Volkamer, and Hans-Peter Lenhof. Reliable anti-cancer drug sensitivity prediction and prioritization. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1):12303, 2024.
- [86] Li Li, Yuxi Fan, and Kuo-Yi Lin. A survey on federated learning. In *2020 IEEE 16th international conference on control & automation (ICCA)*, pages 791–796. IEEE, 2020.
- [87] Linyi Li, Tao Xie, and Bo Li. Sok: Certified robustness for deep neural networks. In *2023 IEEE symposium on security and privacy (SP)*, pages 1289–1310. IEEE, 2023.
- [88] Tenglong Li, Yuqing Zhang, Prasad Patil, and W Evan Johnson. Overcoming the impacts of two-step batch effect correction on gene expression estimation and inference. *Biostatistics*, 24(3):635–652, 2023.
- [89] Xuhong Li, Haoyi Xiong, Xingjian Li, Xuanyu Wu, Xiao Zhang, Ji Liu, Jiang Bian, and Dejing Dou. Interpretable deep learning: Interpretation, interpretability, trustworthiness, and beyond. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 64(12):3197–3234, 2022.

- [90] Zachary C Lipton. The mythos of model interpretability: In machine learning, the concept of interpretability is both important and slippery. *Queue*, 16(3):31–57, 2018.
- [91] Jiashuo Liu, Zheyang Shen, Yue He, Xingxuan Zhang, Renzhe Xu, Han Yu, and Peng Cui. Towards out-of-distribution generalization: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.13624*, 2021.
- [92] Qiang Liu, Pan Li, Wentao Zhao, Wei Cai, Shui Yu, and Victor CM Leung. A survey on security threats and defensive techniques of machine learning: A data driven view. *IEEE access*, 6:12103–12117, 2018.
- [93] WeiKang Liu, Yanchun Zhang, Hong Yang, and Qinxue Meng. A survey on differential privacy for medical data analysis. *Annals of Data Science*, 11(2):733–747, 2024.
- [94] Mohammad Lotfollahi, Mohsen Naghipourfar, Malte D Luecken, Matin Khajavi, Maren Büttnner, Marco Wagenstetter, Žiga Avsec, Adam Gayoso, Nir Yosef, Marta Interlandi, et al. Mapping single-cell data to reference atlases by transfer learning. *Nature biotechnology*, 40(1):121–130, 2022.
- [95] Xueming Luo, Nan Jia, Erya Ouyang, and Zheng Fang. Introducing machine-learning-based data fusion methods for analyzing multimodal data: An application of measuring trustworthiness of microenterprises. *Strategic Management Journal*, 45(8):1597–1629, 2024.
- [96] Saiyue Lyu, Shadab Shaikh, Frederick Shpilevskiy, Evan Shelhamer, and Mathias Lécuyer. Adaptive randomized smoothing: Certified adversarial robustness for multi-step defences. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 37:134043–134074, 2024.
- [97] Karima Makhlouf, Sami Zhioua, and Catuscia Palamidessi. When causality meets fairness: A survey. *Journal of Logical and Algebraic Methods in Programming*, 141:101000, 2024.
- [98] Charles Marx, Shengjia Zhao, Willie Neiswanger, and Stefano Ermon. Modular conformal calibration. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 15180–15195. PMLR, 2022.
- [99] Marc Masana, Idoia Ruiz, Joan Serrat, Joost van de Weijer, and Antonio M Lopez. Metric learning for novelty and anomaly detection. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.05492*, 2018.
- [100] RC Mayer. An integrative model of organizational trust. *Academy of Management Review*, 1995.
- [101] Ninareh Mehrabi, Fred Morstatter, Nripsuta Saxena, Kristina Lerman, and Aram Galstyan. A survey on bias and fairness in machine learning. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)*, 54(6):1–35, 2021.
- [102] Thomas Miconi. The impossibility of " fairness": a generalized impossibility result for decisions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1707.01195*, 2017.
- [103] Matti Minkkinen, Joakim Laine, and Matti Mäntymäki. Continuous auditing of artificial intelligence: a conceptualization and assessment of tools and frameworks. *Digital Society*, 1(3):21, 2022.
- [104] Alexis Morin-Martel. Machine learning in bail decisions and judges’ trustworthiness. *Ai & Society*, 39(4):2033–2044, 2024.

- [105] Lukas Mosser and Ehsan Zabihi Naeini. A comprehensive study of calibration and uncertainty quantification for bayesian convolutional neural networks—an application to seismic data. *Geophysics*, 87(4):IM157–IM176, 2022.
- [106] Bálint Mucsányi, Michael Kirchhof, Elisa Nguyen, Alexander Rubinstein, and Seong Joon Oh. Trustworthy machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.08215*, 2023.
- [107] Allan H Murphy and Robert L Winkler. A general framework for forecast verification. *Monthly weather review*, 115(7):1330–1338, 1987.
- [108] Mahdi Pakdaman Naeini, Gregory Cooper, and Milos Hauskrecht. Obtaining well calibrated probabilities using bayesian binning. In *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*, volume 29, 2015.
- [109] Nina Narodytska and Shiva Prasad Kasiviswanathan. Simple black-box adversarial attacks on deep neural networks. In *CVPR workshops*, volume 2, 2017.
- [110] MZ Naser and Amir Alavi. Insights into performance fitness and error metrics for machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.00887*, 2020.
- [111] Anh Nguyen, Jason Yosinski, and Jeff Clune. Deep neural networks are easily fooled: High confidence predictions for unrecognizable images. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 427–436, 2015.
- [112] Vu-Linh Nguyen, Sébastien Destercke, Marie-Hélène Masson, and Eyke Hüllermeier. Reliable multi-class classification based on pairwise epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Seventh International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, IJCAI-18*, pages 5089–5095. International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence Organization, 7 2018. doi: 10.24963/ijcai.2018/706. URL <https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2018/706>.
- [113] Giovanna Nicora, Miguel Rios, Ameen Abu-Hanna, and Riccardo Bellazzi. Evaluating point-wise reliability of machine learning prediction. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 127:103996, 2022.
- [114] Alexandru Niculescu-Mizil and Rich Caruana. Predicting good probabilities with supervised learning. In *Proceedings of the 22nd international conference on Machine learning*, pages 625–632, 2005.
- [115] Nicolas Papernot, Patrick McDaniel, Somesh Jha, Matt Fredrikson, Z Berkay Celik, and Ananthram Swami. The limitations of deep learning in adversarial settings. In *2016 IEEE European symposium on security and privacy (EuroS&P)*, pages 372–387. IEEE, 2016.
- [116] Nicolas Papernot, Patrick McDaniel, Ian Goodfellow, Somesh Jha, Z Berkay Celik, and Ananthram Swami. Practical black-box attacks against machine learning. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM on Asia conference on computer and communications security*, pages 506–519, 2017.
- [117] Nicolas Papernot, Patrick McDaniel, Arunesh Sinha, and Michael P Wellman. Sok: Security and privacy in machine learning. In *2018 IEEE European symposium on security and privacy (EuroS&P)*, pages 399–414. IEEE, 2018.

- [118] Chunjong Park, Anas Awadalla, Tadayoshi Kohno, and Shwetak Patel. Reliable and trustworthy machine learning for health using dataset shift detection. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 34:3043–3056, 2021.
- [119] Judea Pearl. *Causality*. Cambridge university press, 2009.
- [120] Gabriel I Penagos-Londoño, Carla Rodriguez-Sanchez, Felipe Ruiz-Moreno, and Eduardo Torres. A machine learning approach to segmentation of tourists based on perceived destination sustainability and trustworthiness. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 19: 100532, 2021.
- [121] Rafael Pinot, Florian Yger, Cédric Gouy-Pailler, and Jamal Atif. A unified view on differential privacy and robustness to adversarial examples. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.07982*, 2019.
- [122] Nicolas Posocco and Antoine Bonnefoy. Estimating expected calibration errors. In *International conference on artificial neural networks*, pages 139–150. Springer, 2021.
- [123] Ricardo Trainotti Rabonato and Lilian Berton. A systematic review of fairness in machine learning. *AI and Ethics*, pages 1–12, 2024.
- [124] Khansa Rasheed, Adnan Qayyum, Mohammed Ghaly, Ala Al-Fuqaha, Adeel Razi, and Junaid Qadir. Explainable, trustworthy, and ethical machine learning for healthcare: A survey. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 149:106043, 2022.
- [125] Karoline Reinhardt. Trust and trustworthiness in ai ethics. *AI and Ethics*, 3(3):735–744, 2023.
- [126] Anna Rogers, Olga Kovaleva, and Anna Rumshisky. A primer in bertology: What we know about how bert works. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 8: 842–866, 2021.
- [127] Donald B Rubin. Causal inference using potential outcomes: Design, modeling, decisions. *Journal of the American statistical Association*, 100(469):322–331, 2005.
- [128] Cynthia Rudin. Stop explaining black box machine learning models for high stakes decisions and use interpretable models instead. *Nature machine intelligence*, 1(5):206–215, 2019.
- [129] Mark Ryan. In ai we trust: ethics, artificial intelligence, and reliability. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 26(5):2749–2767, 2020.
- [130] Marco Saerens, Patrice Latinne, and Christine Decaestecker. Adjusting the outputs of a classifier to new a priori probabilities: a simple procedure. *Neural computation*, 14(1):21–41, 2002.
- [131] Spyridon Samonas and David Coss. The cia strikes back: Redefining confidentiality, integrity and availability in security. *Journal of Information System Security*, 10(3), 2014.
- [132] IH Sarker. Machine learning: algorithms, real-world applications and research directions. *sn comput sci* 2: 160, 2021.
- [133] Nadine Schlicker, Kevin Baum, Alarith Uhde, Sarah Sterz, Martin C Hirsch, and Markus Langer. How do we assess the trustworthiness of ai? introducing the trustworthiness assessment model (tram). *Computers in Human Behavior*, 170:108671, 2025.

- [134] Alex Serban, Koen van der Blom, Holger Hoos, and Joost Visser. Practices for engineering trustworthy machine learning applications. In *2021 IEEE/ACM 1st Workshop on AI engineering-software engineering for AI (WAIN)*, pages 97–100. IEEE, 2021.
- [135] Glenn Shafer and Vladimir Vovk. A tutorial on conformal prediction. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 9(3), 2008.
- [136] Hidetoshi Shimodaira. Improving predictive inference under covariate shift by weighting the log-likelihood function. *Journal of statistical planning and inference*, 90(2):227–244, 2000.
- [137] Gordon K Smyth and Terry Speed. Normalization of cDNA microarray data. *Methods*, 31(4): 265–273, 2003.
- [138] Timo Speith. A review of taxonomies of explainable artificial intelligence (xai) methods. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*, pages 2239–2250, 2022.
- [139] Timo Speith, Barnaby Crook, Sara Mann, Astrid Schomäcker, and Markus Langer. Conceptualizing understanding in explainable artificial intelligence (xai): an abilities-based approach. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 26(2):40, 2024.
- [140] William Stallings and Lawrie Brown. Computer security: principles and practice, global edition, 2017.
- [141] Eleni Straitouri, Lequn Wang, Nastaran Okati, and Manuel Gomez Rodriguez. Improving expert predictions with conformal prediction. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 32633–32653. PMLR, 2023.
- [142] Martin Strobel and Reza Shokri. Data privacy and trustworthy machine learning. *IEEE Security & Privacy*, 20(5):44–49, 2022.
- [143] David Stutz, Matthias Hein, and Bernt Schiele. Disentangling adversarial robustness and generalization. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 6976–6987, 2019.
- [144] Tulsi Suchak, Anietie E Aliu, Charlie Harrison, Reyer Zwiggelaar, Nophar Geifman, and Matt Spick. Explosion of formulaic research articles, including inappropriate study designs and false discoveries, based on the nhanes us national health database. *PLoS biology*, 23(5): e3003152, 2025.
- [145] Afnan Sultan, Max Rausch-Dupont, Shahrukh Khan, Olga Kalinina, Andrea Volkamer, and Dietrich Klakow. Transformers for molecular property prediction: Domain adaptation efficiently improves performance. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.03360*, 2025.
- [146] Harini Suresh and John V Guttag. A framework for understanding unintended consequences of machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.10002*, 2(8):73, 2019.
- [147] Christian Szegedy, Wojciech Zaremba, Ilya Sutskever, Joan Bruna, Dumitru Erhan, Ian Goodfellow, and Rob Fergus. Intriguing properties of neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6199*, 2013.
- [148] Elham Tabassi, Kevin J Burns, Michael Hadjimichael, Andres D Molina-Markham, and Julian T Sexton. A taxonomy and terminology of adversarial machine learning. *NIST IR*, 2019: 1–29, 2019.

- [149] Bhavani Thuraisingham. Trustworthy machine learning. *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, 37(1): 21–24, 2022. doi: 10.1109/MIS.2022.3152946.
- [150] Ryan Tibshirani. Conformal prediction. *UC Berkeley*, 2023.
- [151] Ehsan Toreini, Mhairi Aitken, Kovila Coopamootoo, Karen Elliott, Carlos Gonzalez Zelaya, and Aad Van Moorsel. The relationship between trust in ai and trustworthy machine learning technologies. In *Proceedings of the 2020 conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*, pages 272–283, 2020.
- [152] Ehsan Toreini, Mhairi Aitken, Kovila PL Coopamootoo, Karen Elliott, Vladimiro Gonzalez Zelaya, Paolo Missier, Magdalene Ng, and Aad van Moorsel. Technologies for trustworthy machine learning: A survey in a socio-technical context. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.08911*, 2020.
- [153] Wiebke Toussaint and Aaron Yi Ding. Machine learning systems in the iot: Trustworthiness trade-offs for edge intelligence. In *2020 IEEE Second International Conference on Cognitive Machine Intelligence (CogMI)*, pages 177–184. IEEE, 2020.
- [154] Hoa Thi Nhu Tran, Kok Siong Ang, Marion Chevrier, Xiaomeng Zhang, Nicole Yee Shin Lee, Michelle Goh, and Jinmiao Chen. A benchmark of batch-effect correction methods for single-cell rna sequencing data. *Genome biology*, 21(1):12, 2020.
- [155] Dimitris Tsipras, Shibani Santurkar, Logan Engstrom, Alexander Turner, and Aleksander Madry. Robustness may be at odds with accuracy. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.12152*, 2018.
- [156] Ramesh Upreti, Pedro G Lind, Ahmed Elmokashfi, and Anis Yazidi. Trustworthy machine learning in the context of security and privacy. *International Journal of Information Security*, 23(3):2287–2314, 2024.
- [157] Gaël Varoquaux, Alexandra Sasha Luccioni, and Meredith Whittaker. Hype, sustainability, and the price of the bigger-is-better paradigm in ai. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.14160*, 2024.
- [158] Kush R Varshney. Trustworthy machine learning and artificial intelligence. *XRDS: Crossroads, The ACM Magazine for Students*, 25(3):26–29, 2019.
- [159] Kush R Vashney. *Trustworthy machine learning*. Independently published, 2022.
- [160] Kailas Vodrahalli, Tobias Gerstenberg, and James Y Zou. Uncalibrated models can improve human-ai collaboration. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35:4004–4016, 2022.
- [161] Daniël Vos and Sicco Verwer. Efficient training of robust decision trees against adversarial examples. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 10586–10595. PMLR, 2021.
- [162] Vladimir Vovk, Alexander Gammerman, and Glenn Shafer. *Algorithmic learning in a random world*. Springer, 2005.
- [163] Abraham Wald. Statistical decision functions which minimize the maximum risk. *Annals of Mathematics*, 46(2):265–280, 1945.
- [164] Hanchen Wang, Tianfan Fu, Yuanqi Du, Wenhao Gao, Kexin Huang, Ziming Liu, Payal Chandak, Shengchao Liu, Peter Van Katwyk, Andreea Deac, et al. Scientific discovery in the age of artificial intelligence. *Nature*, 620(7972):47–60, 2023.

- [165] Jindong Wang, Haoliang Li, Haohan Wang, Sinno Jialin Pan, and Xing Xie. Trustworthy machine learning: Robustness, generalization, and interpretability. In *Proceedings of the 29th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, pages 5827–5828, 2023.
- [166] Jess Whittlestone, Rune Nyrupe, Anna Alexandrova, and Stephen Cave. The role and limits of principles in ai ethics: Towards a focus on tensions. In *Proceedings of the 2019 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society*, pages 195–200, 2019.
- [167] David Wissel, Nikita Janakarajan, Aayush Grover, Enrico Toniato, María Rodríguez Martínez, and Valentina Boeva. Survboard: standardised benchmarking for multi-omics cancer survival models. *bioRxiv*, pages 2022–11, 2022.
- [168] David Wissel, Daniel Rowson, and Valentina Boeva. Systematic comparison of multi-omics survival models reveals a widespread lack of noise resistance. *Cell Reports Methods*, 3(4), 2023.
- [169] Alexander Wood, Kayvan Najarian, and Delaram Kahrobaei. Homomorphic encryption for machine learning in medicine and bioinformatics. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 53(4): 1–35, 2020.
- [170] Baoyuan Wu, Shaokui Wei, Mingli Zhu, Meixi Zheng, Zihao Zhu, Mingda Zhang, Hongrui Chen, Danni Yuan, Li Liu, and Qingshan Liu. Defenses in adversarial machine learning: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.08890*, 2023.
- [171] Yinhao Wu, Bin Chen, An Zeng, Dan Pan, Ruixuan Wang, and Shen Zhao. Skin cancer classification with deep learning: a systematic review. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12:893972, 2022.
- [172] Pulei Xiong, Scott Buffett, Shahrear Iqbal, Philippe Lamontagne, Mohammad Mamun, and Heather Molyneaux. Towards a robust and trustworthy machine learning system development: An engineering perspective. *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 65:103121, 2022.
- [173] Huan Xu and Shie Mannor. Robustness and generalization. *Machine learning*, 86:391–423, 2012.
- [174] Jingkang Yang, Kaiyang Zhou, Yixuan Li, and Ziwei Liu. Generalized out-of-distribution detection: A survey. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 132(12):5635–5662, 2024.
- [175] Ying Yu, Naixin Zhang, Yuanbang Mai, Luyao Ren, Qiaochu Chen, Zehui Cao, Qingwang Chen, Yaqing Liu, Wanwan Hou, Jingcheng Yang, et al. Correcting batch effects in large-scale multiomics studies using a reference-material-based ratio method. *Genome biology*, 24(1):201, 2023.
- [176] Yu-Jie Zhang, Zhen-Yu Zhang, Peng Zhao, and Masashi Sugiyama. Adapting to continuous covariate shift via online density ratio estimation. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36:29074–29113, 2023.
- [177] Longjian Zhou, Andrew Chi-Hau Sue, and Wilson Wen Bin Goh. Examining the practical limits of batch effect-correction algorithms: When should you care about batch effects? *Journal of Genetics and Genomics*, 46(9):433–443, 2019.

A Research Methods

A.1 GoogleScholar Search

To create Figure 2, we entered the term “trustworthiness machine learning” in Google Scholar in June 2025. We used the default settings of Google Scholar, i.e., any time, sort by relevance, any article type, and including citations but no patents. Table 2 shows the first 30 hits for this search, along with information on whether the article was excluded from our analysis. We excluded articles if one of the following criteria was met:

- not peer-reviewed
- books, commentaries, short tutorials
- out of scope (not about trustworthiness of AI/ML)
- article only partially available

	Paper	Exclusion	Reason for exclusion (if applicable)
1	Toreini et al. [151]	no	
2	Eshete [39]	no	
3	Chandler et al. [21]	no	
4	Vashney [159]	yes	book
5	Thuraisingham [149]	no	
6	Huai [65]	yes	only introduction available
7	Rasheed et al. [124]	no	
8	Kentour and Lu [77]	no	
9	Bayram and Ahmed [10]	no	
10	Hauke et al. [60]	yes	out of scope
11	Park et al. [118]	no	
12	Serban et al. [134]	no	
13	Varshney [158]	yes	commentary nature, short student tutorial
14	Huang et al. [66]	yes	only introduction available
15	Mucsányi et al. [106]	yes	preprint, not peer-reviewed
16	Toreini et al. [152]	yes	preprint, not peer-reviewed
17	Penagos-Londoño et al. [120]	yes	out of scope
18	Wang et al. [165]	yes	course description, only introduction available
19	Luo et al. [95]	yes	out of scope
20	Han et al. [57]	yes	book
21	Toussaint and Ding [153]	no	
22	Xiong et al. [172]	no	
23	Upreti et al. [156]	no	
24	Huertas Celdran et al. [67]	no	
25	Feng et al. [41]	no	
26	Strobel and Shokri [142]	no	
27	Li et al. [89]	no	
28	Morin-Martel [104]	yes	out of scope
29	Cho et al. [24]	yes	preprint, not peer-reviewed
30	Heuer and Breiter [63]	yes	out of scope

Table 2: Top 30 Google Scholar hits.

A.2 PubMed Query

The results depicted in Figure 3 were obtained querying PubMed as described in the following. The results shown in Figure 3a and 3b were obtained in PubMed by using the query

```
(<term>[Title/Abstract] AND (machine learning[Title/Abstract])
```

where <term> was replaced by the respective trustworthiness-related term. Notably, we did not include performance and accuracy, as they are used in almost every ML publication. We retrieved the csv files containing the results per year. As the data retrieval was performed in July 2025, we decided to exclude 2025 from our analysis, and only consider the years until 2024.

To get all ML papers in PubMed per year (as needed for Figure 3c), we used the query

```
machine learning[Title/Abstract]
```

and downloaded the csv with the results per year. Moreover, we queried for all publications containing machine learning and none of the trustworthiness-related terms using

```
((((((((((((((((((((machine learning[Title/Abstract]) NOT (trustworthiness[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (fairness[Title/Abstract])) NOT (interpretability[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (explainability[Title/Abstract])) NOT (auditability[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (transparency[Title/Abstract])) NOT (safety[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (security[Title/Abstract])) NOT (privacy[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (confidentiality[Title/Abstract])) NOT (integrity[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (robustness[Title/Abstract])) NOT (generalizability[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (accountability[Title/Abstract])) NOT (translucency[Title/Abstract]))
NOT (confidence[Title/Abstract])) NOT (reliability[Title/Abstract]))
```

Lastly, we queried for the publications containing machine learning and any of the terms:

```
((((((((((((((((((((trustworthiness[Title/Abstract]) OR (fairness[Title/Abstract]))
OR (interpretability[Title/Abstract])) OR (explainability[Title/Abstract]))
OR (auditability[Title/Abstract])) OR (transparency[Title/Abstract]))
OR (safety[Title/Abstract])) OR (security[Title/Abstract]))
OR (privacy[Title/Abstract])) OR (confidentiality[Title/Abstract]))
OR (integrity[Title/Abstract])) OR (robustness[Title/Abstract]))
OR (generalizability[Title/Abstract])) OR (accountability[Title/Abstract]))
OR (translucency[Title/Abstract])) OR (confidence[Title/Abstract]))
OR (reliability[Title/Abstract])) AND (machine learning[Title/Abstract]))
```